

RECONNAISSANCE SURVEY OF ARCHAEOLOGICAL RUINS

ANTOINETTE PHOOLIYAR, BARLOW
2022-2023 SURVEY REPORT

MAY 2024

Aapravasi Ghat Trust Fund under the aegis of the Ministry of Arts and Cultural Heritage
In collaboration with Mauritian Archaeological Cultural Heritage, Stanford University

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FOREWORD

On behalf of the Aapravasi Ghat Trust Fund Board, I am delighted to present the report of the Reconnaissance Survey conducted collaboratively by our staff and the team of archaeologists from Stanford University.

Antoinette Phooliyar holds immense significance for the Aapravasi Ghat Trust Fund. It is the very place where the first 36 indentured workers from India settled in Mauritius back in 1834. These pioneers laid the groundwork for a system that would later be adopted in the Great Experiment, shaping the movement of over 5 million people worldwide—the indentured labour system.

Antoinette Phooliyar serves as a crucial waypoint in our quest to comprehend this system. It sheds light not only on the contractual aspects affecting subsequent labourers but also on the living and working conditions endured by our forebears. The well-preserved ruins of Antoinette Sugar Estate offer valuable insights, standing as a testament to history. Unlike many other sites across Mauritius, this area remains untouched by modern development pressures that have erased countless historical remnants of sugar estate factories and camps.

Our Reconnaissance Survey uncovers a neglected facet of our past—the lives of labourers—often overlooked in official historical records. Combined with the oral histories shared by the last indentured labourers and their descendants, this survey provides a glimpse into the daily struggles and resilience of common people who have shaped our present and continue to influence our future.

I extend heartfelt gratitude to Terra Mauricia Ltd, the current site owner, for granting us permission to conduct this research. May our collaboration endure, fostering a deeper understanding of our shared heritage.

Mr Rishiraj Kanhye
Chairman

Aapravasi Ghat Trust Fund

INTRODUCTORY NOTE

The Aapravasi Ghat Trust Fund is mandated, *inter alia*, to

- to undertake or support scientific research related to indentured labour and to the Aapravasi Ghat and related sites;
- to set up interpretation centres which shall interpret the cultural heritage of a site in relation to indentured labour;
- to carry out or support archaeological or conservational works on the Aapravasi Ghat and related sites;

Recognizing Antoinette Phooliyar as a crucial milestone in Mauritius' history of indentured labor, the Aapravasi Ghat Trust Fund has been studying the site since 2015. Our collaboration with the local community aims to better understand and highlight the site's significance. This partnership culminated in the annual commemoration, starting from 1st November 2021, honoring the memory of the 36 pioneers who arrived at Antoinette in 1834.

Through the Reconnaissance Survey, we delve into the daily lives of these early laborers—individuals who sought a better life in Mauritius, shaping its destiny. The survey results will guide our 2021 initiative: establishing a Heritage Village. While the Aapravasi Ghat World Heritage Property (AG WHP) and its Interpretation Centre focus on explaining the AG's global importance, the Heritage Village will illuminate the living and working conditions of indentured laborers and their descendants on sugar estate camps. Ultimately, the Heritage Village will immerse visitors in the daily experiences of our ancestors and the Intangible Cultural Heritage (ICH) they brought and nurtured, preserving memories across generations.

Our collaboration with the local community will reach another level with this project. Not only will they help document the site and its history, but they will also play a major role in planning and developing this heritage site as a cultural tourism destination. Their participation in the cultural mapping exercise and the priceless information they shared during the sessions testify to the important role they hold.

I would like to thank the team of archaeologists from Stanford University for sharing their knowledge and expertise, and the various volunteers who helped in the fieldwork.

We're excited to continue our study and make this Heritage Village a reality!

Mr Hariduth Ramgoolam
Director
Aapravasi Ghat Trust Fund

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The Aapravasi Ghat Trust Fund (AGTF) wishes to acknowledge the valuable contribution of all institutions and individuals who assisted in and facilitated the Reconnaissance Survey. In particular, the AGTF would like to acknowledge the Ministry of Arts and Cultural Heritage, Terra Mauricia Ltd, Ministry of Agro-Industry and Food Security, Sugar Industry Labour Welfare Fund, National Heritage Fund, University of Mauritius, Polytechnics Mauritius and Ecole Nationale Supérieure d'Architecture de Nantes (Mauritius), Barlow Senior Citizens Association, residents of Phooliyar Nagar and Mr Dhuny from Barlow Village.

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CITATION

Soodin Runghen, Maurina¹, Krish Seetah², Sasa Caval², Alessandra Cianciosi², and Kiran Chuttoo Jankee¹. 'Reconnaissance Survey of Archaeological Ruins at Antoinette Phooliyar, Barlow'. Aapravasi Ghat Trust Fund, 24 April 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11058715>.

¹Aapravasi Ghat Trust Fund

²Stanford University

ABOUT THE COLLABORATORS

AAPRAVASI GHAT TRUST FUND

The Aapravasi Ghat Trust Fund is a parastatal body under the aegis of the Ministry of Arts and Cultural Heritage. The present project is in line with our mandate to “create public awareness of the history of indentured labour”; “promote the social and cultural aspects of the Aapravasi Ghat and related sites”; and “to undertake or support scientific research related to indentured labour and to the Aapravasi Ghat and related sites”.

The Reconnaissance Survey was also initiated to fulfil the following objectives of the AGTF Research Plan

- **Objective 1:** Research the origins of indenture;
- **Objective 2:** *Multidisciplinary research* [on sites that open up another aspect of indenture including the quarantine system and life on the estates to study];
- **Objective 3:** Research on memory and heritage.

STANFORD UNIVERSITY

Stanford University is collaborating in the Reconnaissance Survey with the Aapravasi Ghat Trust Fund under the Mauritian Archaeology and Cultural Heritage (MACH (Stanford)) Project.

The MACH (Stanford) focuses on bringing the unique and rich archaeological past of Mauritius to a wide audience. Engaging with a multidisciplinary approach to historical archaeology, the project focuses on key sites in Mauritius and is based on a systematic excavation and environmental sampling programme. The underlying aims are to better understand the transition from slavery to indentured labour following abolition, the extent and diversity of trade in the region and the environmental consequences of intense, monoculture, agriculture.

Since 2008, MACH (Stanford) has conducted archaeological research on various sites linked to the history of slavery and indenture in Mauritius. Some sites on which they worked in collaboration with the AGTF include Flat Island Quarantine Station, Ilot Gabriel, Bois Marchand Cemetery, and Trianon Barracks.

PARTICIPANTS

The team from Stanford is led by Dr Krish Seetah, an Associate Professor at Stanford University. Of Mauritian origin, he has been working with the AGTF for more than a decade to help better understand the history of Mauritius and its importance in understanding regional and global slavery and indenture history. He is also the Director of the MACH project. Since 2008, Dr Seetah is leading archaeological research on various sites linked to the history of slavery and indenture in Mauritius. Some sites on which he worked in collaboration with the AGTF include Flat Island Quarantine Station, Ilot Gabriel, Bois Marchand Cemetery, and Trianon Barracks.

Dr Sasa Caval is an Associate Researcher at the Institute of Anthropological and Spatial Studies at the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts. More recently, she has developed her research to incorporate anthropological as well as archaeological perspectives in a study of identity construction, using religion and religious expression by descendent communities on formerly colonised island enclaves; her principal case study is Mauritius.

Dr Alessandra Cianciosi is a post-doctoral scholar. She is a Marie Skłodowska-Curie Fellow in the Amsterdam School for Historical Studies at Universiteit van Amsterdam (Netherlands) and visiting post-doc in the Department of Anthropology, Stanford University. Her research focuses on landscape, the development of settlements, and funerary archaeology.

Ms Stefania Manfio is a maritime archaeologist and current Ph.D. Candidate in the Department of Anthropology at Stanford University. She specialises in the use of 3D visualizations, based on gaming technology, as a tool for the enhancement and dissemination of maritime heritage. Since 2017, Ms Manfio has also been part of the MACH project.

Kiran Chuttoo Jankee, Researcher at the AGTF facilitated the cultural mapping with the local community. Kiran also coordinated with the MBC for the dissemination of information about the site and survey.

The project is coordinated by Maurina Soodin Runghen, Researcher at the AGTF. She actively investigates means of facilitating access to historical information and research results to the public and research community. To this end, she contributed to the concept of history-based performances and coordinated a Roving Exhibition that visited the whole of Mauritius Island. Maurina is currently working on the setting up of a Heritage Village that aims at preserving and promoting indentured labour cultural heritage sustainably.

Volunteers from the various institutions included:

University of Mauritius

- Ashee Seeruttun
- Ourvashi Kumari Domun
- Yogeeta Bhunooa
- Meera Lutchmun

Ecole Nationale Supérieure d'Architecture de Nantes (Mauritius)

- Stephanie Harimalala

Polytechnics Mauritius

- Abhay Viyoman Sharma Tany

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ACRONYMS

AGTF	Aapravasi Ghat Trust Fund
GIS	Geographical Information System
GPS	Global Positioning System
MACH	Mauritian Archaeology and Cultural Heritage
MBC	Mauritius Broadcasting Corporation
MGI	Mahatma Gandhi Institute
Str	Structure
SU	Stratigraphical Unit
TT	Test Trench
VRS	Voluntary Retirement Scheme

INTRODUCTION

In line with the Aapravasi Ghat Trust Fund (AGTF) mandate “to undertake or support scientific research related to indentured labour and to the Aapravasi Ghat and related sites”, a Reconnaissance Survey of the archaeological ruins at Antoinette Phooliyar, Barlow was organised in November-December 2022 and in July 2023. The survey is a continuation of the research initiated in 2015 following a preliminary assessment.

This report describes the survey conducted during November-December 2022 and July 2023. The initial chapter serves as an introduction, setting the context and objectives of the survey. The second chapter presents an overview of the survey site, including its historical background. Methodology and results from the Reconnaissance Survey are presented in the third chapter, while the fourth chapter focuses on community engagement through cultural mapping activities. Chapter five explores how the survey findings were disseminated. Chapter six delves into the historical significance of the site, drawing from survey findings and additional research. The report concludes with a summary of key findings and recommendations for further research initiatives on the site.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

The aim of the Reconnaissance Survey is to use oral history and archaeological techniques to identify and document the ruins and remains of the site more specifically by:

- i. carrying out interviews with the last residents of the sugar estate camp;
- ii. excavating test trenches to obtain stratigraphy to document site evolution of the estate camp;
- iii. producing a structured record of field observations of the site on a Geographical Information System (GIS).

The survey also aims to enhance the capacity of local students in the field by familiarizing them with the techniques and equipment utilized in archaeological research, all under the guidance of experienced scholars.

RATIONAL

The study was planned in line with the objectives of the AGTF Research Plan and the overall AGTF research project for the site, namely to:

- document the history of the sugar estates
- document life on the site
- document the physical remains of the site

- draw up a profile of indentured labourers and other forms of labour utilised on the estates
- understand the spatial distribution on the site; and
- understand the importance of the site in the Mauritian context in the 19th and 20th century.

Antoinette Sugar Estate occupies a prominent place in Mauritian history as the first sugar estate to successfully employ indentured workers from India in 1834 following the abolition of slavery. Originating from Bihar, the initial 36 indentured labourers were the first to experience a system that would later be known as the Great Experiment in the use of ‘free’ labour. This system eventually resulted in the global movement of over 5 million people through the indentured labour system. The survey site holds historical significance as the actual location where the 36 Hill Coolies worked and lived in Mauritius as from 1834.

A joint site visit in 2021 brought attention to the deteriorating state of the ruins of Antoinette Sugar Estate. The structures face imminent risk of being lost if conservation measures are not promptly implemented.

Given the significance of the site in the understanding of the indentured labour system, the AGTF initiated a project to document the remains through a Reconnaissance Survey. This survey complements ongoing research by providing detailed documentation of structures which remain on the site. The results will contribute to a better understanding of the living and working conditions of the enslaved, Ex-Apprentices, and indentured labourers of Indian, Chinese, African and Mauritian origin who worked and lived on the sugar estate.

ANTOINETTE PHOOLIYAR

THE SURVEY SITE

Antoinette Phooliyar is situated near the village of Barlow, in the district of Rivière du Rempart in the Northeast of Mauritius. A study of Rouillard¹ and Descubes² confirmed that the site was originally part of the Antoinette Sugar Estate. **Figure 1** shows the survey site and the delimitation of Antoinette Sugar Estate as depicted by Descubes in the 1880 Map of Mauritius compiling Government triangulation estate plans and title deeds. Within the survey site of Antoinette Phooliyar lie remnants of the 19th century sugar estate core area, with the ruins of the sugar mill and vestige of the estate camps. **Figure 2** illustrates the digitized 1880 estate boundary superimposed on aerial imagery, highlighting the identified archaeological remnants within the present-day context.

Figure 1: Map showing the delimitation of Antoinette Sugar Estate in Descubes (1880)

¹ Guy Rouillard, *Histoire des Domaines Sucriers de l'île Maurice* (Les Pailles, Ile Maurice: The General Printing and Stationery Company Limited, 1974), 76–77.

² Descubes, A, *Map of the Island of Mauritius / Compiled from the Government Triangulation Estate Plans, Title Deeds, & from Many Other Sources*, cartographic material, 1:63 630 (Mauritius: Public Works Department, 1880), <http://nla.gov.au/nla.obj-231272435>.

Figure 2: Map showing digitized 1880 estate boundary superimposed on aerial imagery

HISTORICAL BACKGROUND

The sugar estate was originally established by Joseph Dioré in 1828 after he purchased and merged 17 plots of land to create Belle Alliance Sugar Estate³. Four years later, Belle Alliance covered 502 Arpents when it was purchased by Hunter, Arbuthnot & Co⁴. The estate was renamed to *Antoinette*, by Raoul de Maroussem and his associates in 1863⁵. Despite changes in ownership and area over the years, this area is still known as Antoinette.

PHYSICAL EVOLUTION OF THE SUGAR ESTATE

1770 – 1782: 1st concession but no development

The first concession for this area was given in 1770 to Chevalier de Chermont, a French military officer and aristocrat. However, he did not develop the land and returned to France in 1782⁶.

1782 – 1815: 2nd concession with first development

The land was then given in concession to Sieur Louis Naud, another French settler who transformed it into a “*small estate where he grew some sugar, spices, and vegetables...and for grazing by livestock*”⁷. By 1810, it had become a sugar estate, with a small sugar factory which also produced alcohol. The estate was successful enough for it to expand to more than 500 arpents⁸. After Naud passed away in 1815⁹, the estate was parcelled into 17 lots and sold to different buyers.

1828 – 1830: the beginning of Belle Alliance

In 1828, the 17 plots were bought and consolidated by the new owners Emilien Dupuy and Mr and Mrs Joseph Dioré¹⁰ to create the Belle Alliance Sugar Estate¹¹. By 1830, Belle Alliance included “*a small stone sugar mill, a rum distillery, and store house,*”¹² and covered 300 arpents.

³ Rouillard, *Histoire des Domaines Sucriers de l’Ile Maurice*, 76.

⁴ Ibid., 84.

⁵ Ibid., 77.

⁶ Satyendra Peerthum, ‘The Making of a Garden of Sugar & Its Slender Complex Historical Threads’: A Historical and Pictorial Presentation of Antoinette Sugar Estate & The Experiences of Its Indentured Labourers and Their Descendants (Phooliyar)’ (Draft under review, n.d.), 24.

⁷ Ibid., 27.

⁸ Ibid.

⁹ Ibid.

¹⁰ Ibid., 28.

¹¹ Rouillard, *Histoire des Domaines Sucriers de l’Ile Maurice*, 76.

¹² Peerthum, ‘The Making of a Garden of Sugar & Its Slender Complex Historical Threads’: A Historical and Pictorial Presentation of Antoinette Sugar Estate & The Experiences of Its Indentured Labourers and Their Descendants (Phooliyar)’, 28.

1832 - 1848: expansion of Belle Alliance

In 1832, Belle Alliance was sold to Hunter and Arbuthnot Company, a newly formed British company based in Mauritius¹³. An 1832 map describes the estate as having a sugar mill, storage areas, a rum distillery, stables, the owner's house, slaves quarters and other buildings¹⁴. By the time Hunter and Arbuthnot Company sold Belle Alliance, it covered 793 arpents¹⁵.

1863 - 1883: Belle Alliance becomes Antoinette and expands further

Belle Alliance was purchased and renamed Antoinette by Raoul de Maroussem and associates in 1863¹⁶. In the 1870s, Maroussem hired 4 Liberated Africans who were also stone masons, who along with 19 other labourers, were instrumental in building a bigger sugar factory in 1871, a larger sugar chimney and expanding the camp for indentured workers in 1878¹⁷.

1883 – 1920: Ste Gustave Martin and the 1892 cyclone

After Mr Gustave Martin purchased Antoinette Sugar Estate in 1883, it was expanded to more than 2,000 arpents¹⁸. However, the 1892 cyclone caused major destruction with the loss of 75% of crops and Rs. 25,000 worth of damaged property¹⁹. After a long recovery, Antoinette Sugar Estate saw better days with the renovation of the sugar factory and new expensive machinery by 1910²⁰.

HISTORICAL INFORMATION ABOUT THE ESTATE CAMP

Estate camps originally housed slaves, but were later repurposed for indentured labourers. These lodgings became an obligation with Ordinance 31 of 1867, under which the employer was bound to provide indentured labourers on a country Estate with “*sufficient and wholesome lodgings*”²¹. The proximity to the factory and sugarcane plantation ensured control over their movements. Since indentured labourers worked from dawn to dusk, the little time they spent at the estate camps were precious. These camps were not only their sleeping quarters, but also provided a social and cultural environment that supported them in enduring their harsh living conditions.

Preliminary historical research describes the modifications made to the estate camps on Antoinette Sugar Estate to accommodate increasing number of indentured labourers.

¹³ Peerthum, ‘The Making of a Garden of Sugar & Its Slender Complex Historical Threads’: A Historical and Pictorial Presentation of Antoinette Sugar Estate & The Experiences of Its Indentured Labourers and Their Descendants (Phooliyar)’, 29.

¹⁴ Ibid., 29–30.

¹⁵ Rouillard, *Histoire des Domaines Sucriers de l’Ile Maurice*, 84.

¹⁶ Ibid., 77.

¹⁷ Peerthum, ‘The Making of a Garden of Sugar & Its Slender Complex Historical Threads’: A Historical and Pictorial Presentation of Antoinette Sugar Estate & The Experiences of Its Indentured Labourers and Their Descendants (Phooliyar)’, 63–66.

¹⁸ Ibid., 91.

¹⁹ Ibid., 91–92.

²⁰ Ibid., 91–93.

²¹ Ibid.

In 1864, Marousseem instructed the estate manager to expand the estate camp to 13 long barracks made of straw and wood to accommodate around 600 men, women and children²². At around the same time, a five meter deep well was also dug to provide workers with water. In 1878, the camp was further expanded to accommodate 300 more people.

In 1901 Martin further expanded the camp to cater for more than 1,000 persons. The camp would then consist of “more than 20 long barracks made of straw and wood that could accommodate between 50 to 55 men, women, and children”²³

Further research is needed to better understand the origin and physical evolution of estate camps on Antoinette Sugar Estate.

PREVIOUS AND ONGOING RESEARCH

The AGTF initiated historical research on Antoinette Phooliyar in 2014. The results of the research were published in the form of a booklet²⁴ which briefly describes the sugar estate in the 19th century. It also provides information about the first indentured labourers recruited on the estate and the contract which they signed. The conditions working and living conditions they were promised in this contract set the model adopted in the *Great Experiment*. Following more detailed research, a book on the site is being prepared by the AGTF²⁵. The book is expected to provide more information about the evolution of the sugar estate and its remains, and about some of the labourers who were employed on the estate.

Between 2006 and 2009, the AGTF conducted a project titled “*From Indenture to VRS*” to collect testimonies of descendants of indentured labourers and of people involved in life on sugar camps to have an overview of the indentured experience in Mauritius. Around 500 interviews²⁶ were conducted all over Mauritius at the time, a dozed of which were targeted at Antoinette Phooliyar. The targeted respondents either lived or worked on Antoinette Sugar Estate. During these interviews, the respondents shared their recollections of life on the sugar estate and camp during the early 20th century²⁷. The Oral History Research is being further developed through a

²² Peerthum, ‘The Making of a Garden of Sugar & Its Slender Complex Historical Threads’: A Historical and Pictorial Presentation of Antoinette Sugar Estate & The Experiences of Its Indentured Labourers and Their Descendants (Phooliyar)’, 67–69.

²³ Ibid., 98.

²⁴ Satyendra Peerthum, *Antoinette (Phooliyar): An Invitation to Discover the Indenture Heritage of Mauritius* (Port Louis, Mauritius: Aapravasi Ghat Trust Fund, 2015).

²⁵ Peerthum, ‘The Making of a Garden of Sugar & Its Slender Complex Historical Threads’: A Historical and Pictorial Presentation of Antoinette Sugar Estate & The Experiences of Its Indentured Labourers and Their Descendants (Phooliyar)’.

²⁶ Maurina Soodin Runghen and Kiran Chuttoo Jankee, ‘Intangible Cultural Heritage Linked to Indenture’ (Presentation, Research Unit meeting, Aapravasi Ghat Trust Fund, 2019).

²⁷ Chuttoo Jankee, “Oral History Project on Antoinette Sugar Estate at Phooliyaar Nagar and Barlow” Pg 18–19.

collaborative project with the Mahatma Gandhi Institute²⁸. During this project, the residents of Phooliyar Nagar and Barlow will be interviewed about the daily life of the indentured labourers and their descendants. The former was created when the last residents of Antoinette Sugar Estate were relocated²⁹. The latter village initially consisted mainly of workers of the sugar estate and those who provided goods and services to the sugar estate, its camps and residents.

In 2015, a site visit was conducted on the site by MACH (Stanford), who made a preliminary map showing the location of potential archaeological remains. The results of the survey are discussed in detail in the section “[Preparation for the Survey](#)” in Chapter 4. **Figure 3** shows the condition of the ruins in 2015.

Figure 3: Remains of Antoinette sugar factory in 2015

In 2021, during an official site visit, the state of the remains was noted and the Reconnaissance Survey was planned. The advanced rate of vegetation growth and deterioration of remains can be seen at **Figure 4**.

Figure 4: (a) Condition of chimney and mill area in 2021; (b) Condition of remains in camp in 2021

²⁸ Maurina Soodin Runghen, ‘Proposal for Joint Project with the MGI Department of Bhojpuri, Folklore & Oral Traditions for a Study of Some of the Oldest Families in Barlow Village and Phooliyar Nagar’, Unpublished Reports (Port Louis: Aapravasi Ghat Trust Fund, July 2023).

²⁹ Chuttoo Jankee, Pg 18.

THE SURVEY

Archaeologists use reconnaissance methods to locate and record sites and features that represent significant human use of the landscape. It is an important stage in archaeological research that allows the understanding of the site layout and use. The survey constitutes a preliminary assessment of an area through topographic surveys, site inspections, and documentation of standing structures and features. For surface features, such as buildings and roads, both topographic and planimetric maps are used³⁰. During this process, the distribution of surviving features is also studied and recorded.

The survey will result in a detailed photo-documentation of each standing historical building and structure and the terrestrial mapping of historical parts of the sugar estate. These will provide a better understanding of the living and working conditions of the enslaved, Ex-Apprentices, and indentured labourers of Indian, Chinese, African and Mauritian origin who worked and lived on the sugar estate.

PREPARATION FOR THE SURVEY

Prior to starting the Reconnaissance Survey, a surface survey was carried out to locate possible sites, objects and structures. The area was investigated by walking across it, examining artifacts on the surface, and recording their approximate location together with that of any surface features. Special attention was given to topographical occurrences such as trenches, holes, outcrops and clusters of trees. Data was taken from aerial imagery (Google Earth) and incorporated into the situation imagery. Structures identified at the time are shown in the map at **Figure 5**.

While incorporating the data from the aerial imagery, some interesting data became apparent. Those were visualized only on the aerial imagery (orange line, west of the central area) and have been added to the document purely for information. The reasons for these crop marks are unknown, and no information has been found in historical sources about any additional road or structure apart from the ones existing today.

³⁰ Renfrew and Bahn, *Archaeology: Theories, Methods, and Practice: Theories, Methods, and Practice*, Pg 87.

Figure 5: Map showing area surveyed in 2015

MAPPING OF HISTORICAL FEATURES AND REMAINS

Figure 6: Mapping using Total Station

Mapping is the key to the accurate recording of most survey data. For surface features, such as buildings and roads, both topographic and planimetric maps are used³¹. During this process, the distribution of surviving features is studied and recorded.

During the survey, structures were documented according to the general minimum standards accepted by the archaeological profession. Coordinates of individual structures were determined by means of the Global Positioning System (GPS) and plotted on a map. **Figure 6** shows the use of the Total Station to record the position of the structures accurately.

SURVEY OF HISTORICAL STRUCTURES

The survey of the historical part of the estate incorporated documenting, photographing, and recording the standing architecture of the estate. Features and structures documented included the ‘pool’, the standing walls of the sugar factory, the chimney, the labourer’s building, and the concrete structures in Camp 1.

Each feature was sketched, measured, and documented. A general description focused on the shape, level of preservation, building material and possible historical use were documented using the MACH database as seen in **Figure 7**.

Detailed documentation of the standing architecture is critical for the assessment of the preserved historic structures, for the preparation of a current preliminary plan of the estate and to plan all future work. This was essentially the evaluation of the current situation on the estate, to assess the number and state of the historical structure on which all the future planning will be based.

All feature descriptions produced during the survey are included at **Annex 1**.

³¹ Renfrew and Bahn, Pg 87.

Figure 7: Sample of structures description in MACH database

PHOTOGRAMMETRY

Photogrammetry is a technique that utilises rectified photographs for the documentation of a site or feature³². Images are taken as the photographer moves around the subject being recorded, and the camera is either handheld or mounted to a portable tripod. These photographs are then rectified to produce a set of photographs accurate enough to be used to measure distances. Anderson Richard C.³³ views it as an important tool for the archaeologist, as it is thorough, instantaneous and systematic. It records everything that is visible passively, without disturbing fragile features; and the level of accuracy is achieved through metric control and can result in 3D drawings or renderings of a feature.

Photogrammetry creates accurate fully textured 3D models from photographs and can be used to capture a range of subjects from the smallest objects to entire landscapes. From this data, 3D models, videos and orthoimages (scaled images with no distortion or perspective), can be created to allow for more accurate and complete interpretative site drawings than ever before. Drone surveys use photogrammetry to produce landscape models and orthographic images. The same principles can be applied with hand-held cameras to create models of artefacts, site features and buildings.

³² Ibid., 526.

³³ C. Richard Anderson, 'Photogrammetry: The Pros and Cons for Archaeology', *World Archaeology* 14, no. 2 (October 1982): 200, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00438243.1982.9979860>.

Figure 8: (a) Preparation of sketches of structures; (b) Placing markers for photogrammetry

During the survey, sketches of the structures were prepared to facilitate documentation (See **Figure 8 (a)**). High resolution pictures of the structures were then taken after placing markers to facilitate rectification and processing (See **Figure 8 (b)**). After the processing of the images architectural plan and/or 3D models of those buildings will be performed.

30GB of images were taken to create a 3D model of the pool (See **Figure 9**), the labourer's building, and orthophotos of concrete buildings in Camp 1 (Str. 105, 106, and 107). Regarding Str. 104, it was possible to document the gradual process of deterioration of the building by comparing the state of preservation in November 2022 and July 2023, after the collapse of a side wall (See **Figure 10**).

Figure 9: 3D reconstruction of Str 100

Figure 10: 3D reconstruction of Str 104

TEST TRENCHES

Archaeological excavations assist in the identification, definition, uncovering, dating and interpretation of an archaeological site³⁴. Test trenches are a first step in this direction, as they are a rapid and relatively inexpensive method of archaeological evaluation used to estimate the archaeological potential of a site. The trenches help show what an area has to offer, and help identify the extent of a possible site, while analysis and plotting of the material retrieved from them by screening (sieving) of the soil can produce maps showing areas with high concentrations of different kinds of artifacts³⁵. During this process, features unearthed are accurately recorded through scaled drawings and photography. Artefacts found during the excavations are also documented and analysed, while features unearthed are accurately recorded through scaled drawings and photography.

Archaeological excavations were performed in CAMP 1 sugar estate, east of the production area of the estate. According to the oral histories, there used to be two lines of three buildings, standing parallel to each other. On each side of these concrete living structures for the workers, there were also thatch-covered individual houses, where the labourers lived. These latter do not exist anymore, indeed every sign of them had been erased. Out of the two lines of concrete buildings only the southeastern two buildings exist, both in an extremely poor state of preservation.

In the area of CAMP 1, 4 test trenches (A, B, C, D) of various sizes were excavated (See **Figure 11**: Map showing the location of the trenches). Two test trenches were placed between the main structures (Structures 106 and 107), while two others were situated either across the wall of a structure (Str 108) or next to it (Str 107).

The excavations were stratigraphic, and we identified 2 to 3 stratigraphical units (SU), also known as layers, in each TT. The depth of the TT varied between 10 to 40 cm from the topsoil.

³⁴ L. Peter Drewett, *Field Archaeology: An Introduction* (London: University College London Press, 2003), 107.

³⁵ Renfrew and Bahn, *Archaeology: Theories, Methods, and Practice: Theories, Methods, and Practice*, 95.

Figure 11: Map showing the location of the trenches

TT A (See **Figure 12 (a)**) was set between buildings 1 and 2 and was of 2,0 x 3,0 size. TT B (See **Figure 12 (b)**) was dug next to the eastern (back) wall of structure 2 and was of 2,0 x 1,0 dimensions. The TT C (See **Figure 12 (c)**) was set across the eastern wall of structure 4, the middle of the first line of concrete living structures. This building is completely ruined but we could identify the eastern wall in the terrain. The TT was set across an outside wall and measured 2,0 x 1,0 m. The last TT, TT D, was situated in the middle between the two lines of concrete barracks, in an area where there should have been the second of the two external kitchens. The TT measured 2,0 x 2,0 m.

Figure 12: (a) Test Trench A; (b) Test Trench B; (c) Test Trench C

With the survey and archaeological excavations of the Antoinette – Phooliyar sugar estate we now have an adequate picture of the central industrial part of the estate and part of the living areas for the labourers. Apart from receiving information about the industrial archaeological records, we also have the first information about the living areas for labourers, supported by their material culture, albeit only from the middle of the 20th century.

ARTEFACTS CATALOGUING AND ARTEFACTS

According to Renfrew and Bahn³⁶, when artefacts are collected during excavations, they must be documented. The documentation includes inter alia the location where the artefact was discovered; its condition; its material; its potential historical use; and its measurements. Initial sorting is done, to categorise the artefact based on the material such as glass, bottle, ceramic, pottery, metal object and wooden object. Each category is then classified into smaller more manageable groups. This classification is also commonly done based on three kinds of characteristics or attributes, namely surface attributes (including decoration and color); shape attributes (dimensions as well as shape itself); and technological attributes (primarily raw material).

³⁶ Ibid., 119.

In all 4 test trenches, approximately 300 objects of various material types, uses, and chronology, were gathered, some of which were fragmented or heavily corroded. **Figure 13** depicts some of the fragments gathered from Test Trench A.

Figure 13: Some artefacts gathered during excavations

Artefacts were recorded based on the TT and SU where they were located. Each artefact has a site code, TT and SU information, a brief description and dimensions recorded (See Figure 15 (b)). The artefacts have been catalogued by recording all the information listed in **Figure 14**.

Site code	PO23 (meaning: Phooliyar 2023)
TT information	TT A
Layer information	SU 2
Brief description	fragment of an iron nail
Length	2,3 cm

Figure 14: Example of information collected during cataloguing

Every artefact was also photographed and allocated a photo ID (See **Figure 15 (a)**).

Figure 15: (a) Photographing and allocating an ID during cataloguing; (b) Taking measurements during cataloguing

PRELIMINARY FINDS INFORMATION

At the preliminary survey of the CAMP1 and the initial cleaning, we found many objects of recent use and origin, especially metal artefacts related to the current use of the area as an orchard.

METAL: Objects from metal were made from iron, lead, bronze, and other material, and of industrial or home daily use. We found coins (including one 5 cents coin dated to 1964), nails, screws, washers, hooks and rings, large iron rods, and chisels.

GLASS: Artefacts from glass include window glass, bottles, bowls including sugar bowls, cups including teacups, bracelets, perfume and ink bottles, and marbles. We cannot set the chronology at present; however, the preservation and some of the materials themselves are indicative of a period of use from at least the end of the 19th century.

POTTERY, CERAMICS, PORCELAIN: were recovered from all trenches and included examples of earthenware oil lamps, containers, tableware, and cooking pots. The chronology of these finds is hard to determine due to the fragmentation of the artefacts. However, the cohort of finds included rice bowls made from Chinese porcelain, blue-decorated colonial tableware, 19th-century stoneware bottles, modern plates, and containers.

BONES and SHELLS: All the bone materials are of animal origin, likely from a goat. Shells are of various sizes, some of which are substantial, indicating that they were likely collected and brought back to the homestead for decorative purposes.

The character of the finds is diverse. They include objects of industrial use, related to the sugar estate's mechanical work. The construction of metal and glass objects indicates the use of dwellings until the 1980s. The majority of the artefacts represent the daily life of a community of sugar estate workers that lived on the camp; for example, tableware and glassware, decorative items, items of personal use (toothbrush), and jewellery (glass bracelets, gems). One particularly interesting find was a slate board with engraved horizontal lines, as was commonly used in schools throughout Mauritius.

Many artefacts clearly belonged to children, such as the glass marbles, providing an important insight into a portion of the indentured community – children – which has remained entirely obscured.

All the finds were discarded purposely or lost accidentally.

CULTURAL MAPPING WITH THE LOCAL COMMUNITY

“Cultural Mapping is the application of diverse tools and methodologies to collect data that give a multi-dimensional image and spatial understanding of the “cultural character” of a community embedded in its environment.”³⁷. Stewart describes it as “a process of collecting, recording, analyzing and synthesizing information in order to describe the cultural resources, networks, links and patterns of usage of a given community or group”³⁸. It is used by the communities to help identify their cultural assets, both tangible and intangible by enabling the representation of complex layers of information about people, places, and their history, thus representing a holistic and inclusive perspective of culture. It is thus useful in various processes, especially where a bottom-up approach is adopted³⁹, namely, in documenting cultural resources, empowering the local community, transmission of local knowledge systems, promoting intercultural dialogue, cultural resource management, and community economic development⁴⁰.

During the Reconnaissance Survey, the participation of the local community was crucial as it provided the archaeologists with the opportunity to query some of the last residents of the sugar estate camp. Few records are available about the daily life of indentured workers or their descendants on at Antoinette Sugar Estate. The cultural mapping exercise is thus instrumental in understanding the site by providing input from the life experienced of the people who lived and worked on the estate.

³⁷ Ayesha Pamela Rogers, *Cultural Mapping Manual: A Guide for Planning and Carrying out Cultural Mapping in Pakistan* (Islamabad, Pakistan: UNESCO Islamabad, 2008), 6.

³⁸ S. Stewart, ‘Cultural Mapping Toolkit’, Toolkit (Vancouver: Creative City Network of Canada and 2010 Legacies Now, 2007), 8.

³⁹ Nancy Duxbury, W.F Garrett-Petts, and David MacLennan, eds., *Cultural Mapping as Cultural Inquiry*, 1st ed., Routledge Advances in Research Methods (New York: Routledge, n.d.), 2.

⁴⁰ Rogers, *Cultural Mapping Manual: A Guide for Planning and Carrying out Cultural Mapping in Pakistan*.

Figure 16: Cultural mapping with the local community

The local community participated through a formal on-site interview (See **Figure 16**), an on-site chance conversation with a sugarcane plantation worker and lengthy conversations with Mr D Dhuny MSK, an elderly gentleman who grew up near the camp but spent his childhood and youth on the estate.

The formal interview was with a few of the last residents of the estate camp, who were relocated to the nearby Phooliyar Nagar in the 1970s and 1980s. They talked about the room allocation on the estate camp and even showed the approximate location of parts of the estate camps that have since been destroyed. (See **Figure 17**).

Figure 17: Dr. Seetah (in the middle) interacting with the local community to understand the spatial distribution

They also talked about life on the estate and the importance and possible locations of important landmarks in the camp life such as the Baitka, Chinese shop and Kalimaye. Through the

conversation with them, we also learnt about the social structure on the camp and the way the sugar estate impacted their relationships.

Among the many incidents they narrated, was the death of one of the single men on the estate camp. Since he was single with no family on the camp or in the neighbourhood, the camp took care of his last rites, while the Estate provided his coffin. They described how the wake was held in the Baitka and how the whole camp followed the funeral procession in the morning until they reached the official entrance of the Estate, at which point the women and children were told to go back to the camp while the men went on. It is interesting to note that the women did not go to the cemetery. They had an idea of where it could be found: a place they called *ganasso* which was overgrown with eucalyptus trees, but were not sure, since they had never been there. We also learnt that once a person is buried, there was no rite which required the physical presence of the relatives near the tomb.

The sugarcane plantation worker informed us that he was born in the estate camp. During his childhood his parents moved away when they were able to afford to buy land in a neighbouring village. However, the connection to the area and the land is still strong as he is now working on the same estate. He told us an interesting anecdote about the regular visits of the doctor on the bicycle, how the children would run away, fearing injections, and how the residents would slip the doctor a coin in the hope of more speedy medication when they were sick.

Mr Dhuny MSK, described the unity amongst the people living in the camp. It was interesting to learn that the same baitka was used by three different linguistic groups in harmony for the education of the children and gathering of the elders. They learnt hindi, marathi and telegu in the same baitka, although the majority ended up speaking Bhojpuri as it was the most commonly used language. In addition, the same space was used for the community prayers in which everybody participated irrespective of origin.

The conversations with the local community helped better understand the social conditions of the people living and working on the estate, and helped in interpreting some of the findings from the trenches and in understanding the spatial distribution of the area surrounding the estate camp.

EQUIPMENT USED

The tools and equipment used in the survey can be categorised as follows:

Site cleaning tools	To remove vegetation from features and clear test trench areas Example: rakes, leaf blowers, machetes, saws
Digging tools	To uncover features and artefacts Example: shovels, pickaxes, hoes, shears
Detailed digging tools	To uncover finer details of features and/or uncover artefacts without damaging them Example: brushes, dust pans, trowels
Tools to carry soil	To move soil during excavation and to backfill the trenches after excavation and documentation Example: wheelbarrows, buckets

Recording artefacts, features and trenches	To produce measured drawings of trenches and features, record information about uncovered artefacts Example: clipboards, pencils, paper, zipper bags, markers, measuring taps, metric sticks, scales, calipers, database for artefacts cataloguing
Mapping tools	To precisely locate all features on a digital map Example: Total Station Leica FlexLine TS03, Apple iPadPro with iPencil and Lenovo ThinkPad with GIS software
Photography and Photogrammetry tools	To document the features and artefacts Example: Nikon D80 and 5300 cameras, tripod, markers
Safety tools	Must be available on-site to ensure safety of all present on site Example: First-aid Kit

DISSEMINATION OF INFORMATION AND SITE AWARENESS

OPEN DAY

In order to disseminate information on the importance of the site, the methods utilised by the archaeologists and the preliminary findings of the Reconnaissance Survey, an Open Day was organised on 26 July 2023. AGTF Board Members and staff; staff from the Parent Ministry; representatives from Terra Mauricia Ltd, and the various collaborating institutions; the local community and the national television channel were invited to the site. The visitors were thus able to see the different activities undertaken by the archaeologists and volunteers during the survey, namely excavation of test trenches and recording of artefacts.

The visit consisted of a guided visit of the remains of the estate camp from which residents were relocated in the 1980s (See **Figure 18**). The information gathered during the multidisciplinary research being undertaken by AGTF and Stanford University was presented. These fields of research include historical research, oral history and archaeology. Emphasis was laid on how the disciplines complement each other.

Figure 18: Guided visit and explanations by Dr Seetah (far left) to visitors during Open Day on 26 July 2023

In addition to the Open Day, arrangements were also made with the National TV Channel, MBC, to disseminate information about the site and research. Information about the site and Reconnaissance Survey was aired in MBC News on 30 July 2023⁴¹ (See Figure 19).

Figure 19: Interviews by the MBC News Section aired in French on MBC 1 and in Bhojpuri on MBC 4 on 30 July 2023

SPECIAL PROGRAMS ON THE NATIONAL TELEVISION

The archaeological survey and cultural mapping carried out in Phooliyar Antoinette were the focus of 3 episodes of the Virasat⁴² program as follows:

1. *Virasat Phooliyar- Broadcast on 26th July, 2023*⁴³

Local inhabitants were interviewed for the program together with the director of AGTF, Mr Chand Ramgoolam. The latter talked on the importance of this archaeological survey and highlighted the contribution on indentured immigrants in shaping Mauritius at all levels. Mrs Neela Periasamy is one of the inhabitants of Phooliyar and she was emotional while entering the ruins of her house, she meticulously described the cohabitation arrangements in the estate camp. Mrs Sakoon Appadu talked about the daily routine of her in laws at work and the family members at home. Her focus was mainly on cooking and food when she was newly married and came to live in this sugar estate. Mr D Dhuny described the unity that prevailed among all the neighbors, regardless of communities. He mentioned the baitka, the Kalimaye and the Chinese shop that had a key role in the sugar estate. Mrs Saroda Hurkooo talked about the natural calamities which affected the sugar estate, especially the estate camps and how they took shelter in baitkas. Mr Siven Mootusami talked about the different tasks performed in the sugar cane fields by labourers and how the tasks and wages differed according to their age groups.

⁴¹ News in French: https://mbcproduction.mbconline.xyz/jt/july/jt_30_07_2023.mp4

News in Bhojpuri: https://mbcproduction.mbconline.xyz/samachar/july/sam_30_07_2023.mp4

News in English: https://mbcproduction.mbconline.xyz/news/july/etv_30_07_2023.mp4

⁴² Virasat is a 15-17 mins program broadcast on Wednesdays on TV channel MBC 3 at 20hrs. Produced jointly by the AGTF and the MBC, it aims at disseminating information about the history and heritage of Mauritius.

⁴³ <https://youtu.be/fDFyrKjNaOg>

2. *Virasat Phooliyar part 2- Broadcast on 2nd August, 2023*⁴⁴

This virasat program was the 2nd segment on the archaeological survey. It included the reaction of the Second Secretary of High Commission of India, Mrs Sunita Pahuja. Mr Manoj Sitiah, a labourer talked of his childhood, about his recollections of the place and doctors coming to visit them regularly to check malaria infection.

3. *Virasat Phooliyar Part 3- Broadcast on 10th August, 2023*⁴⁵

The 3rd segment of the Archeological digging focused on the reaction of and explanation by the chairman of AGTF and the reaction of the Vice Chairman of AGTF and Chairman of Prof Basdeo Bissoondoyal Trust Fund Guruji Jhummun. Although they did not grow at Antoinette, they talked about their experiences on the sugar estates near which they grew up.

Figure 20: Virasat episodes dedicated to the site and the Reconnaissance Survey

4. *Encounter program - Broadcast on 3rd August, 2023*⁴⁶

Archaeologists, Dr Krish Seetah and Dr Alessandra Cianciosi, were the guests in a special episode of Encounter⁴⁷. The episode was animated by Mrs Kiran C Jankee with whom they discussed Archaeology, the Archeological survey at Phooliyar and different archaeological projects they have been working on in Mauritius.

Figure 21: Special Encounter Program by the MBC at Antoinette Phooliyar

⁴⁴ <https://youtu.be/p84SbugzXpU?si=SkcwylPHltvFK84>

⁴⁵ <https://youtu.be/-eNPJl8zSKU?si=NpWSKayhrx2YaylL>

⁴⁶ <https://youtu.be/oc2KaioMzQY?si=YffXaLQFPRmHw5Lf>

⁴⁷ Encounter is a 30-minute program broadcast every Monday on MBC 1 as from 20.00hr. It covers motivational speakers, philosophers, spiritual personalities, as well as other people who have very unique skills.

HISTORICAL SIGNIFICANCE

The Antoinette Phooliyar site includes remains of the sugar mill and last inhabited estate camp. It is the place where thousands of people lived and worked, including more than 400 Mozambican, Malagasy, and Indian slaves between the 1770s and 1830s; around 4,000 Indian, Chinese, African indentured labourers between 1830s and 1950s; and Mauritian workers of Indian and Afro-Malagasy or Creole descent, especially during the sugar cane harvest period⁴⁸. The site therefore provides a unique setting to understand life on a successful sugar estate in the 18th and 19th centuries. This understanding is even more important as it can help understand a system that affected the life of over 5 million people in British, French and Spanish colonies under the indentured labour system.

The system started with the first successful contract signed between 36 Hill Colliers from Bihar and Hunter-Arbuthnot & Company, as an experiment in the use of ‘free’ labour after the abolition of slavery. These 36 Hill Coolies were recruited in Calcutta for a 5-year contract by George Charles Arbuthnot of Gillanders acting on behalf of Hunter-Arbuthnot & Company⁴⁹. The labour contract, which these labourers signed, was written in Bengali. The salient features of the contract are summarised in the 1875 Report⁵⁰ as follows:

- The monthly pay was Rs.5 for the men, and Rs.4 for the women⁵¹;
- The employer would also provide them food and clothing;
- They had all received 6-months pay in advance in Calcutta and the journey to Mauritius was paid by Hunter Arbuthnot & Company;
- One rupee was deducted from their monthly wages by Hunter Arbuthnot & Company for the return passage to India.
- Their work would consist of digging holes, weeding canes, or working in the sugar-house

This contract would later, be adopted during the *Great Experiment* in the use of “free” labour under the indentured labour system that would lead to the movement of over 5 million people to British, French and Spanish colonies.

Phooliyar was the name of one of the settlements on the Estate, which has since disappeared. According to the oral interviews carried out by Baishali Ghosh, it might be a Bhojpuri distortion of

⁴⁸ Peerthum, *Antoinette (Phooliyar): An Invitation to Discover the Indenture Heritage of Mauritius*, 1.

⁴⁹ Peerthum, *Antoinette (Phooliyar): An Invitation to Discover the Indenture Heritage of Mauritius*, 3.

⁵⁰ ‘Report of the Royal Commissioners Appointed to Enquire into the Treatment of Immigrants in Mauritius Presented to Both Houses of Parliament by Command of Her Majesty’, Royal Commission, February 1875, 27–28, HathiTrust.

⁵¹ although there was no woman in the first group

the Tamil words Pillayar or Pulayas. The first is a popular Tamil name of Lord Ganesha. The second word, Pulaya denotes a social group of Tamil origin who came to Mauritius as indentured labourers in the 1830s⁵².

On the other hand, according to Mr Dhuny, one of the oldest residents of Barlow, who spent his childhood on the estate camp, the local community believes that the name Phooliyar was given to the area to illustrate the determination of the first 36 to flourish⁵³ in this new land (flourish translated in bhojpuri).

Although the exact location of the camp inhabited by the first 36 is not known, the local community believes that the camp was located at or in the vicinity of the Phooliyar camp. The continuity in use of the camp which was extended with straw huts as and when needed indicates that the location was demarcated for labourers' accommodation. The labourers were thus close to the factory, which would have been at the centre of all the estate's activities.

The sugar estate was not only the place where these people lived and worked. It was also the starting point for many who became contractors or business owners. Khodabux became a job contractor after his contract ended. He supplied skilled and semi-skilled contract workers to Antoinette Sugar Estate⁵⁴. Asseen started as a skilled worker on the sugar estate. However, he later established his own wood workshop in the capital⁵⁵.

The continuous land use from the time the original estate was created in 1782 to the present time has ensured little disturbance to the historical and archaeological features on the site. These provide a good indication of the close relationship between the its people, camp and the sugar factory and the activities related to sugarcane cultivation and sugar production.

⁵² Ghosh Baishali, 'Le site de Phooliyar à Maurice : l'empreinte de la mémoire des migrations', *Carnets de Recherches de l'Océan Indien*, 2019.

⁵³ Flourish is loosely translated as phoolo in Mauritian Bhojpuri

⁵⁴ Peerthum, 'The Making of a Garden of Sugar & Its Slender Complex Historical Threads': A Historical and Pictorial Presentation of Antoinette Sugar Estate & The Experiences of Its Indentured Labourers and Their Descendants (Phooliyar)', 52.

⁵⁵ Peerthum, *Antoinette (Phooliyar): An Invitation to Discover the Indenture Heritage of Mauritius*, 5.

SUMMARY AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The Reconnaissance Survey included a thorough investigation to gather preliminary information about the site's condition, significance and potential for preservation. Apart from receiving information about the industrial archaeological records, it was also possible to gather information about the living areas for labourers, supported by their material culture, albeit only from the middle of the 20th century.

HISTORICAL SIGNIFICANCE

The Antoinette Phooliyar site includes remains of the sugar mill and last inhabited estate camp. It is the place where thousands of people lived and worked, including the enslaved, Ex-Apprentices, and indentured labourers of Indian, Chinese, African and Mauritian origin. The continuous land use from the time the original estate was created in 1782 to the present time has ensured little disturbance to the historical and archaeological features on the site. These provide a good indication of the close relationship between the its people, camp and the sugar factory and the activities related to sugarcane cultivation and sugar production. The site therefore provides a unique setting to understand life on a successful sugar estate in the 18th and 19th centuries. This understanding is even more important as it can help understand a system that affected the life of over 5 million people in British, French and Spanish colonies under the indentured labour system.

CURRENT CONDITION OF THE REMAINS

The current owner, Terra Mauricia Ltd, dedicates this area to the same activities that were historically present, namely sugarcane plantation and fruit tree (litchi) cultivation. Subsequently, the remains are not in danger of being pulled down due to development pressure. Some attempts at stabilising structures such as the chimney were noted. One of the historical buildings has been converted to a garage for sugarcane lorries, with apparent minimal change to the original building. The remaining structures have remained undisturbed. However, the presence of invasive vegetation have also been noted. Left unchecked, this vegetation could potentially harm the structures and lead to the loss of very important elements in understanding the site.

ACCESSIBILITY

The remains are found in a private land owned by Terra Mauricia Ltd and are accessible only to its employees. The AGTF and MACH (Stanford) team was granted access for the survey. The Open Day was an occasion to ensure that the rich heritage value of the site would be disseminated to the public through the local media. On the other hand, the entrance of the site, i.e where the Lotus Monument is found is accessible to the public and is visited by thousands of visitors, both local and foreign. An information panel was placed by the AGTF in 2016 near the Lotus Monument to provide information about the site history and importance.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Following the reconnaissance survey, the following recommendations were made:

- (a) To conduct more in-depth research in historical sources to
 - a. locate the original camp allocated to the 36 Hill Coolies and determine its relation to the later camps;
 - b. understand the physical evolution of the site and its components. Potential sources identified are land transaction records and inventories of assets found in the Registrar General's collection and the Notaries papers at the National Archives Department. Additional information may also be found in the reports of site visits in the writing of the Protector of Immigrants' Reports and Commission of Enquiry Reports;
- (b) To continue working with the local community to better understand the use and value of the site from the perspective of the people who lived and worked on the site;
- (c) To carry out further documentation of the remains;
- (d) To preserve the Antoinette Phooliyar site for future generations by preventing further deterioration.

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ANNEX 1: DESCRIPTION OF HISTORICAL FEATURES

Stanford MACH, Mauritian Archaeology and Cultural Heritage						Survey / Feature Form	
Feature n.	Site / project Name	Year	Survey Date	Area	SiteCode	SiteSurvey_code	Survey_Code
100	Phooliyar Sugar Estate	2022	30/11/2022	Factory	PSE	00057	PSE2022_Survey_1
	Definition	Reliability of identification		Degree of Preservation - Site		Accessibility	
	Closed/Open Water Pools	Excellent				Adequate	
	Surface Visibility	Vegetation type		Geomorfology	Notes on Hydrology		
Chronology	80	%	Agricultural growth				
	Coordinates (central point)		X	Y		Z	
Description	Photo1		Photo2				
<p>Rectangular building, square corners. Basalt stones. No roof but inside the building is divided in 2 cisterns (one smaller SE and one bigger NE) Between the 2 cisterns there is a wall 147 cm with a channel 29 cm. The wall inside in covered with plaster (completely overgrown by vegetation). 1) Short side in the southwest we have 3 buttress (Short side 9 m); 2) Southeast building is much preserved and have 8 buttresses (5 well preserved; 1 destroyed and 2 base). 3) Short Northeast side no buttress only straight wall (base 8m). Iron tube coming out from the middle of the wall with a lot of mortar around it, probably added or restored in a second time. 4 markers for the photogrammetry. 4) Long northwest side 4 buttress bad preserved (Long side 30 m). It looks likes that the buttress have been added in a second stage, probably immediately after. Iron ring in the corner. 8 markers for the photogrammetry. Measures with total station, no prism.</p>							
			General Notes				
Flora	Soil Type	Rock Typology	Stones Size	Form filled by			
Sugar Cane	Loam	Igneous	Cut stones	AC-SM-SC			
Artificial Finds	Organic Finds		Links with	Site Director			
				KS			
References_Historical Sources							

Stanford MACH, Mauritian Archaeology and Cultural Heritage				Survey / Feature Form			
Feature n.	Site / project Name	Year	Survey Date	Area	SiteCode	SiteSurvey_code	Survey_Code
101	Phooliyar Sugar Estate	2022	30/11/2022	Factory	PSE	00058	PSE2022_Survey_1
	Definition	Reliability of identification		Degree of Preservation - Site		Accessibility	
	Mill	Adequate		Poor		Adequate	
	Surface Visibility	Vegetation type		Geomorfology		Notes on Hydrology	
	30	%	Grass				
Chronology	Coordinates (central point)			X	Y	Z	
1871							
Description	Face building of probably a mill, close to the chimney are. It is preserved only the main façade (tot 22.50 m).			Photo1	Photo2		
	1) It has a big door (292wide; 65 thick; length ?) with an arch shape, on the left side there is a hinge; and one window top left in the main facade.						
	2) another window and door in the lower right part, probably an extension of the main building. Under this second window (132x92) there is a huge iron pipe (diametrically esterno 32cm) coming out from the front wall while Inside there is a hole. The door presents two steps (290x152); on the right side there are two holes probably for the hinges						
	A window on the top with an Arabic shape and two roof stones decorated. Under this there is a inscription in a frame [A1871M].						
Flora	Soil Type	Rock Typology	Stones Size	General Notes			
Fruit Orchard	Loam	Igneous	Cut stones				
Artificial Finds		Organic Finds					
	Links with						
References_Historical Sources				Form filled by AC-SM-SC Site Director KS			

Stanford		MACH, Mauritian Archaeology and Cultural Heritage					Survey / Feature Form	
Feature n.	Site / project Name	Year	Survey Date	Area	SiteCode	SiteSurvey_code	Survey_Code	
102	Phooliyar Sugar Estate	2022	30/11/2022	Factory	PSE	00059	PSE2022_Survey_1	
	Definition	Reliability of identification		Degree of Preservation - Site		Accessibility		
	Chimney	Excellent		Excellent		Adequate		
	Surface Visibility	Vegetation type		Geomorfology	Notes on Hydrology			
	80	%	Grass					
Chronology	Coordinates (central point)		X	Y	Z			
	1870							
Description	Photo1		Photo2					
	<p>Chimney still well preserved. Frame with date [1876?]. Measures 5.22 x 5.22 m On the SW side there is the door with an arch shape for the fire. (1.07 wide; 1.04 length; 1.03 thick). The door is at 210 from left side and 207 from the right.</p>							
Flora	Soil Type	Rock Typology	Stones Size					
Fruit Orchard	Loam	Igneous	Cut stones					
Artificial Finds	Organic Finds		General Notes					
			Links with		Form filled by			
					AC-SM-SC			
					Site Director			
					KS			
References_Historical Sources								

Stanford				MACH, Mauritian Archaeology and Cultural Heritage			Survey / Feature Form	
Feature n.	Site / project Name	Year	Survey Date	Area	SiteCode	SiteSurvey_code	Survey_Code	
103	Phooliyar Sugar Estate	2022	30/11/2022	Factory	PSE	00060	PSE2022_Survey_1	
	Definition	Reliability of identification		Degree of Preservation - Site		Accessibility		
	Windmill	Adequate		Adequate		Adequate		
	Surface Visibility	Vegetation type		Geomorfology		Notes on Hydrology		
Chronology	80	%	Grass					
Description	Coordinates (central point)			X	Y	Z		
	Base of a wind mill, circular shape, made from masoned basalt blocks and a cement mortar. It is composed by 5 levels/circles. The bottom level has an opening in the E side. The diameter max on the top is 2.97m. The top has a hole in the middle with a pipe and 4 nails coming out, and other iron bars , with six (out of eight originally) pairs of big iron screws also demonstrating there was something substantial and heavy attached to the top. There seems to be big iron rods leading from the windmill to the chimney - pairs of iron rods with metal pipe around it - it appears like they were holding something, maybe a pipe coming from the windmill to the chimney (?.?).			Photo1	Photo2			
Flora	Soil Type	Rock Typology	Stones Size	General Notes				
Sugar Cane	Loam	Igneous	Cut stones					
Artificial Finds	Organic Finds			Links with				
References_Historical Sources				Form filled by AC-SM-SC Site Director KS				

Stanford		MACH, Mauritian Archaeology and Cultural Heritage				Survey / Feature Form	
Feature n.	Site / project Name	Year	Survey Date	Area	SiteCode	SiteSurvey_code	Survey_Code
104	Phooliyar Sugar Estate	2022	30/11/2022	Laborer	PSE	00061	PSE2022_Survey_1
	Definition	Reliability of identification		Degree of Preservation - Site		Accessibility	
	Stone Structure	Poor		Adequate		Good	
	Surface Visibility	Vegetation type		Geomorfology		Notes on Hydrology	
Chronology	40	%	Agricultural growth				
Description		Coordinates (central point)		X	Y	Z	
<p>Stone building, probably infirmary. No roof preserved and the NW wall is completely destroyed. Some corners collapsed due to roots. The walls are white washed with quick lime inside and outside.</p> <p>1) The long wall in the SE direction has 2 doors (128x257x55), arch shape (tot length 280), the doors has iron hinges in both sides; two steps (16cm); some red painting around the doors. Measures 13 m length and 3.44m tall.</p> <p>2) the short wall in the NE side has many iron hooks on different height (tot length 6.84m)</p> <p>In a corner a piece of iron is coming out from the top. Unearthed floor is fragmented but relatively well-preserved. Vestige of red (wax?) coating at the base of outer and inner walls including at the base and along door openings.</p> <p>Base of outer door opening (left) shows an extruding but broken line of bricks (steps?) while base of outer door opening (right) has an intact stone step, into which is inlaid a singular ochre brick. The brick has letters (COW, M?) carved into it.</p> <p>Two prominent stone shelves atop the door openings (respectively, slightly to the side). A rusted metal pipe protrudes from the base (center) of the NE wall.</p>		Photo1		Photo2			
				General Notes			
Flora	Soil Type	Rock Typology	Stones Size	Links with			
Fruit Orchard	Loam	Igneous	Cut stones				
Artificial Finds	Organic Finds						
				Form filled by AC-SM-SC Site Director KS			

Stanford MACH, Mauritian Archaeology and Cultural Heritage				Survey / Feature Form			
Feature n.	Site / project Name	Year	Survey Date	Area	SiteCode	SiteSurvey_code	Survey_Code
105	Phooliyar Sugar Estate	2022	01/12/2022	Camp 1	PSE	00062	PSE2022_Survey_1
	Definition	Reliability of identification		Degree of Preservation - Site		Accessibility	
	Kitchen	Excellent		Excellent		Excellent	
	Surface Visibility	Vegetation type		Geomorfology		Notes on Hydrology	
Chronology	70	%	Agricultural growth	Plain			
1900	Coordinates (central point)			X	Y	Z	
Description				Photo1	Photo2		
Concrete block building without roof separated in 2 parts, 1 door and 1 window each unit with a concrete table and fire place, kitchen area							
Flora	Soil Type	Rock Typology	Stones Size				
Fruit Orchard	Loam	Igneous	Cut stones				
Artificial Finds	Organic Finds		General Notes		Form filled by		
			Preliminary survey in Nov 2022		AC-SM-SC		
			Links with		Site Director		
			106 107 108 109		KS		
References_Historical Sources							
Very recent building probably used until the last phase of use of the camp (1980s)							

Stanford		MACH, Mauritian Archaeology and Cultural Heritage					Survey / Feature Form	
Feature n.	Site / project Name	Year	Survey Date	Area	SiteCode	SiteSurvey_code	Survey_Code	
106	Phooliyar Sugar Estate	2023	20/07/2023	Camp 1	PSE	00063	PSE2023_Survey_1	
	Definition	Reliability of identification		Degree of Preservation - Site		Accessibility		
	Barrack	Excellent		Good		Good		
	Surface Visibility	Vegetation type		Geomorfology	Notes on Hydrology			
	70	%	Litchis trees plantation	Plain				
Chronology	Coordinates (central point)			X	Y		Z	
1900								
Description	Photo1			Photo2				
<p>Barracks 2 made of basalt stones and loam probably divided by the other barrack by a path/passage. Here we have preserved 5 chambers/separators with a window and a door each. Very similar to the barrack 107. Tot length 9.70m; the wide of the short north side is 5.10m. One of the wall that divided the two chambers have an opening (door) connecting the two rooms.thickness of the wall: 58 cm. Ruined for all sides except western side, partially preserved. Windows and separators in cement added more recently than the original building. Cement also added among stones of perimeters walls only outside. In correspondence of the five doors there are big carved stones used as jambs. 4 doors were closed with cement (remained on site or ruined close to them). The only door remained open was the one on the southern side. The building was covered with metal corrugate (removed) and the roof was slightly inclined from East to west. Cleaning outside on the western side red wax painting is still visible and partially preserved as a frame for the doors.</p>								
Flora	Soil Type	Rock Typology	Stones Size	General Notes				
Fruit Orchard	Loam	Igneous	Cut stones	Preliminary survey Nov 2022. Proper clearing and survey July 2023				
				Form filled by AC-SM-SC				
				Site Director KS				
Artificial Finds		Organic Finds	105	107	108	109		
References_Historical Sources								

Stanford MACH, Mauritian Archaeology and Cultural Heritage				Survey / Feature Form			
Feature n.	Site / project Name	Year	Survey Date	Area	SiteCode	SiteSurvey_code	Survey_Code
107	Phooliyar Sugar Estate	2022	01/12/2022	Camp 1	PSE	00064	PSE2022_Survey_1
	Definition	Reliability of identification		Degree of Preservation - Site		Accessibility	
	Barrack	Excellent		Good		Good	
	Surface Visibility	Vegetation type		Geomorfology	Notes on Hydrology		
	70	%	Litchis trees plantation	Plain			
Chronology	Coordinates (central point)			X	Y		Z
1900							
Description				Photo1	Photo2		
<p>Barrack made by basalt stones and loam(see STR 106). It is composed by 6 chambers with a window each unit at the same distance. The windows presents 6 horizontal metal bars in the middle and have a frame by white mortar with a reddish color. Cement separators and windows added recently as STR 106. Southern and western sides mostly ruined. Only two cement separators still standing. In trench B (1,5x1m), close to eastern wall, we found its foundations, made of small rock pebbles -40 cm from top soil). No mortar only recent cement among the external surface.</p>							
Flora	Soil Type	Rock Typology	Stones Size	General Notes Preliminary survey Nov 2022. Proper clearing and survey July 2023 Form filled by AC-SM-SC Site Director KS			
Fruit Orchard	Loam	Igneous	Cut stones				
Artificial Finds		Organic Finds					
References_Historical Sources				Links with 106 105 108 109			

Stanford				MACH, Mauritian Archaeology and Cultural Heritage			Survey / Feature Form		
Feature n.	Site / project Name	Year	Survey Date	Area	SiteCode	SiteSurvey_code	Survey_Code		
108	Phooliyar Sugar Estate	2022	01/12/2022	Camp 1	PSE	00065	PSE2022_Survey_1		
	Definition	Reliability of identification		Degree of Preservation - Site		Accessibility			
	Wall	Excellent		Adequate		Good			
	Surface Visibility	Vegetation type		Geomorfology		Notes on Hydrology			
	70	%	Litchis trees plantation	Plain					
Chronology	Coordinates (central point)			X	Y		Z		
1970									
Description				Photo1	Photo2				
Wall to delineate the camp 1. Made by basalt stones different size Poorly preserved. The total length is 44m and it's wide approximately is 170cm. The yard is 16.10m wide									
Flora	Soil Type	Rock Typology	Stones Size						
Fruit Orchard	Loam	Igneous	Cut stones						
Artificial Finds	Organic Finds		General Notes						
				Links with					
				106	107	105	109		
References_Historical Sources								Form filled by AC-SM-SC Site Director KS	

Stanford		MACH, Mauritian Archaeology and Cultural Heritage					Survey / Feature Form	
Feature n.	Site / project Name	Year	Survey Date	Area	SiteCode	SiteSurvey_code	Survey_Code	
109	Phooliyar Sugar Estate	2022	01/12/2022	Camp 1	PSE	00066	PSE2022_Survey_1	
	Definition	Reliability of identification		Degree of Preservation - Site		Accessibility		
	Stone Structure	Poor		Poor		Good		
	Surface Visibility	Vegetation type		Geomorfology		Notes on Hydrology		
Chronology	10	%	Litchis trees plantation					
Description	Coordinates (central point)		X	Y		Z		
			Photo1	Photo2				
	<p>Base of a stone structure very close to the camp wall. This is the NW wall of the second sets of structures - living quarters for the laborers. Together with the STR 108 they were the two parallel longer walls of the houses for indentured laborers.</p>							
Flora	Soil Type	Rock Typology	Stones Size					
Fruit Orchard	Loam	Igneous	Cut stones					
Artificial Finds	Organic Finds		General Notes					
			Links with					
			109	107	106	105		
References_Historical Sources								
							Form filled by	
							AC-SM-SC	
							Site Director	
							KS	

Stanford		MACH, Mauritian Archaeology and Cultural Heritage					Survey / Feature Form	
Feature n.	Site / project Name	Year	Survey Date	Area	SiteCode	SiteSurvey_code	Survey_Code	
110	Phooliyar Sugar Estate	2023	27/07/2023	Factory	PSE	00067	PSE2023_Survey_1	
	Definition	Reliability of identification		Degree of Preservation - Site		Accessibility		
	House	Very Good		Poor		Adequate		
	Surface Visibility	Vegetation type		Geomorfology		Notes on Hydrology		
Chronology	30	%	Dense bush vegetation					
Description		Coordinates (central point)		X	Y	Z		
<p>Basalt block- built structure. Preserved only W wall, with one opening - an arched window (1,35m x 2,20m). Thickness of the wall is 60 cm. The window has remains of closure accessories visible in the stone -photo. On the outside, the wall has still some of the iron hinges and fittings visible. On the N side, the wall is completed - not a ruin. The corner of this structure is preserved only little bit- just enough to see that the E wall was also 60 cm thick. On the S side is a wall of another structure. The roof was semicircular shape and non existing anymore. On the inside of the structure, in the middle between the window (2.70m away) and the edge of the wall (2.70m) is a niche , w/d/h - 80 x 25 x 170cm. The stone shelf/ console for the wooden beams that held the ceiling are 2.90m high. Left of the niche and to the corner with the S edge of the building is a rectangular base, dimensions 1.70 x 0.70 m.</p>		Photo1		Photo2				
Flora	Soil Type	Rock Typology	Stones Size	General Notes				
Fruit Orchard	Loam	Igneous	Cut stones					
Artificial Finds		Organic Finds						
References_Historical Sources				Links with	Form filled by			
				111	AC-SM-SC			
					Site Director			
					KS			

Stanford MACH, Mauritian Archaeology and Cultural Heritage				Survey / Feature Form			
Feature n.	Site / project Name	Year	Survey Date	Area	SiteCode	SiteSurvey_code	Survey_Code
111	Phooliyar Sugar Estate	2023	27/07/2023	Factory	PSE	00068	PSE2023_Survey_1
	Definition	Reliability of identification		Degree of Preservation - Site		Accessibility	
	Factory	Poor		Poor		Adequate	
	Surface Visibility	Vegetation type		Geomorfology		Notes on Hydrology	
Chronology	40	%	Dense bush vegetation				
	Coordinates (central point)			X	Y		Z
Description				Photo1	Photo2		
<p>A long wall with windows and doors (WDWWW- 5 windows, two doors). The dimensions are: 1,30x0,60x2,25 / 1,68x0,66x2,95 / 1.35x0.66x2.28 / 1.27x0.60x2.30 / 1.25x0.55x 2.30 / 1.97x0.60x 3.40 / 1.30x0.50x2.10. On the inside the wall has attached platform, about 5.20m wide, extending between the end of the first window left of the first door and the beginning of the last door. At the corner with str 110 and first window left of the first door is a 2.0m wide platform. The larger platform seems to be a base for some kind of a larger metal machine liked with the sugar processing, while the narrower is part of a landing or steps. The stone beam carriers on the inside of the building are at the 3.0 m height, and are two above each opening, one on each side. The preserved height of the wall is 5,0 to 5,30m.</p>							
Flora	Soil Type	Rock Typology	Stones Size	General Notes			
Fruit Orchard	Loam	Igneous	Cut stones				
Artificial Finds	Organic Finds		Links with		Form filled by		
			110		AC-SM-SC		
References_Historical Sources					Site Director		
					KS		

Stanford				MACH, Mauritian Archaeology and Cultural Heritage			Survey / Feature Form	
Feature n.	Site / project Name	Year	Survey Date	Area	SiteCode	SiteSurvey_code	Survey_Code	
112	Phooliyar Sugar Estate	2023	28/07/2023	Factory	PSE	00069	PSE2023_Survey_1	
	Definition	Reliability of identification		Degree of Preservation - Site		Accessibility		
	Stone Structure	Very poor		Adequate		Very poor		
	Surface Visibility	Vegetation type		Geomorfology		Notes on Hydrology		
Chronology	40	%	Grass					
Description	Coordinates (central point)			X	Y	Z		
	Historical building, still in use. No access.			Photo1	Photo2			
Flora	Soil Type	Rock Typology	Stones Size					
Orchard	Loam	Igneous	Cut stones					
Artificial Finds	Organic Finds		General Notes					
References_Historical Sources	Links with							
						Form filled by AC-SM-SC Site Director KS		

ANNEX 2: CATALOGUE OF ARTEFACTS

ID	SITE	AREA/ST	TRENCH	SU-	MATERIAL	Description/type	Object	Dimensions	Picture	date
1	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	Surface	Glass	Fragment of a colourless glass vessel	glassware	Thick: 0.3cm, l:3.8,w:2.5	387-416	19/07/
2	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	Surface	Glass	Fragment of brown glass vessel	glassware	Thick: 0.5cm; l:1.9, w:2.0	387-416	19/07/
3	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	Surface	Glass	Fragment of green glass	glassware	Thick: 0.5cm, l:2.0, w:1.7	387-416	19/07/
4	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	Surface	Glass	Fragment of green glass	glassware	Thick: 0.4cm, l:3.1, w:2.7	387-416	19/07/
5	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	Surface	Glass	Fragment of a colourless glass vessel	glassware	Thick: 0.4cm,l:2.3, w:1.6	387-416	19/07/
6	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	Surface	Porcelain	Fragment of tableware, decoraterd with yellow and	tableware	Thick: 0.3cm-0.4cm, l:2.2,	387-416	19/07/
7	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	Surface	Metal	Fragment of Nail	nail	l:2.2cm	417-432	19/07/
8	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	Surface	Metal	Nail	nail	l:2.6	417-432	19/07/
9	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	Surface	Metal	Nail	nail	l:4.5	417-432	19/07/
10	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	Surface	Metal	Metal screw with washer	screw	l:6.7, 2r washer:1.8	417-432	19/07/
11	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	Surface	Metal	Metal object with screw boring, shaped into a hook	screw	l:9.4	431, 432	19/07/
12	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	Surface	Metal	Metal washer	washer	2r:2.2	435,436	19/07/
13	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	Surface	Metal	Lead circular object with a hole	lead washer	2r:2.5	433, 434	19/07/
14	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU 1	Glass	Fragment of green glass base	bottle	l:2.8, w:1.2, thick base:0.3-	437-440	21/07/
15	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU 1	Glass	Fragment of a colourless glass vessel	glassware	Thick: 0.2cm, l:2.9	437-440	21/07/
16	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU 1	Porcelane	Fragment of a bowl, painted blue inside and light	rice bowl	Thick: 0.5cm, l:3.0, w:2.5	437-440	21/07/
17	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU 1	Clay	Fragment of earthen lamp base	oil lamp	thick: 0.3cm- 0.5cm,	437-440	21/07/
18	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU 1	Metal	Fragment of metal	unknown	l:1.7cm	437-440	21/07/
19	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU 1	Organic	Fragmented big kauri sea shell	sea shell	l:4.9	437-440	21/07/
20	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU 2	Glass	Fragment of a colourless window glass	window	Thick: 0.2cm, l:2.6	445-441	21/07/
21	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU 2	Glass	Fragment of a colourless glass vessel	glassware	l:1.8, thick:0.1	445-441	21/07/
22	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU 2	Glass	Fragment of a colourless base	glassware	l:1.4, thick:0.1	445-441	21/07/
23	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU 2	Glass	Fragment of a rim of colourless cup	cup	l:2.9, thick:0.3	445-441	21/07/
24	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU 2	Glass	Fragment of a colourless glass vessel	glassware	l:3.2, thick:0.3	445-441	21/07/
25	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU 2	Glass	Fragment of a colourless glass with relief decoration	bowl	l:2.7, Thick: 0.3cm	445-441	21/07/
26	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU 2	Glass	Fragment of a light green glass vessel	glassware	l:2.8, thick:0.2	445-441	21/07/
27	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU 2	Stoneware	Fragment of bottle or cup, decofrated on ther	tableware	l:2.8,Thick: 0.6cm	445-441	21/07/
28	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU 2	Porcelain	Fragment of tableware	tableware	l:2.5, Thick: 0.4cm	445-441	21/07/
29	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU 2	Porcelain	Fragment of tableware	tableware	l:1.7,Thick: 0.4cm	445-441	21/07/
30	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU 2	Clay	Fragment of earthen lamp base	oil lamp	height:2.1, Thick: 0.3cm	445-441	21/07/
31	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU 2	Porcelain	Fragment of tableware	tableware	l:1.4, Thick: 0.2cm	445-441	21/07/
32	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU 2	Metal	Fragment of metal object	unknown	l:3.6	445-441	21/07/
33	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU 2	Metal	Fragment of a nail	nail	l:2.9, thick:0.3	445-441	21/07/
34	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU 2	Organic	Fragment of sea shell	sea shell	l:3.2	448-446	21/07/

Annex 2: Catalogue of Artefacts

ID	SITE	AREA/ST	TRENCH	SU-	MATERIAL	Description/type	Object	Dimensions	Picture	date
35	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU 2	Glass	Fragment of blue glass container - shoulder?	ink bottle	l:3.4,Thick: 0.3cm	448-446	21/07/
36	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU 2	Glass	Fragment of a colourless glass vessel with relief	glassware	l:5.4,Thick: 0.2cm	448-446	21/07/
37	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU 2	Glass	Fragment of a colourless base cup with 5-arm star	cup	height:3.3, base Thick: 0.6,	448-446	21/07/
38	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU 2	Ardoise	8 fragments of slate board, with engraved lines for	slate board	whole l:13.0, thick: 0.2	449-456	21/07/
39	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU 2	Clay	Fragment of earthen lamp rim	oil lamp	l:4.3, Thick: 0.4cm	448-446	21/07/
40	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU 3	Glass	Fragment of a colourless window glass	window	l:2.7,Thick: 0.2cm	457-475	25/07/
41	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU 3	Porcelain	Fragment of a rim of a cup, decorated with dark	cup	l:2.7, Thick: 0.3cm	457-475	25/07/
42	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU 3	Clay	Fragment of rim of earthen lamp	oil lamp	l:2.1, Thick: 0.3cm	457-475	25/07/
43	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU 3	Clay	Fragment of earthen lamp	oil lamp	l:2.8, Thick: 0.4cm	457-475	25/07/
44	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU 3	Glass	Green coloured base of a bottle with indication of	bottle	l:4.8, Thick: 0.5-0.8cm	457-475	25/07/
45	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU 3	Glass	Green coloured wall of a bottle	bottle	l:6.0, Thick: 0.3cm	457-475	25/07/
46	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU 3	Glass	Fragment of base of dark brown glass	bottle	l:5.9, Thick: 1.0cm	457-475	25/07/
47	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU 3	Metal	Fragment of metal object	unknown	l:5.7, Thick: 1.1cm	457-475	25/07/
48	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU 3	Plastic	Toothbrush	toothbrush	l:16.0cm	457-475	25/07/
49	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	C	SU 1	Ardoise	Fragment of slate board	slate board	l:5.9, Thick: 0.2cm	476-499	21/07/
50	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	C	SU 1	Stoneware	Fragment of rim of bowl or cup, glazed white with	bowl or cup	l:3.3,Thick: 0.4cm	476-499	21/07/
51	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	C	SU 1	Stoneware	Fragment of tableware glazed white and with blue	tableware	l:1.4, Thick: 0.3cm	476-499	21/07/
52	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	C	SU 1	Glass	Fragment of brown glass of square shape,with	bottle	l:7.0, w:3.3,Thick: 0.4cm	476-499	21/07/
53	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	C	SU 1	Glass	Fragment of brown glass bottle	bottle	l:3.5,Thick: 0.3cm	476-499	21/07/
54	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	C	SU 1	Glass	Fragment of green bottle mouth and neck with	bottle	l:9.4, 2r lip:2.8, thick wall:	476-499	21/07/
55	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	C	SU 1	Glass	Fragment of a colourless window glass	window	l:10.0,Thick: 0.6cm	476-499	21/07/
56	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	C	SU 1	Glass	Fragment of a colourless window glass	window	l:3.4,Thick: 0.2cm	476-499	21/07/
57	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	C	SU 1	Glass	Fragment of a colourless cup base	cup	height:4.0, 2r base:4.3,	476-499	21/07/
58	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	C	SU 1	Glass	Fragment of a colourless glass vessel	glassware	l:6.9, Thick: 0.3cm	476-499	21/07/
59	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	C	SU 1	Glass	Fragment of a colourless glass vessel	glassware	l:3.3,Thick: 0.3cm	476-499	21/07/
60	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	C	SU 1	Glass	Fragment of a colourless neck of a small square	bottle	l:3.1, 2r of neck:1.6, Thick:	476-499	21/07/
61	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	C	SU 1	Glass	Fragment of a colourless mouth and neck of a	bottle	l:6.8, 2r lip:2.5, Thick: 0.2	476-499	21/07/
62	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	C	SU 1	Glass	Fragment of a colourless shoulder of bottle, very	bottle	l:5.2, Thick: 0.5cm	476-499	21/07/
63	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	C	SU 1	Glass	Fragment of rectangular bottle base, light blue	bottle - SAMPLE	l:4.6, w:3.8, Thick: 0.3cm	476-499	21/07/
64	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	C	SU 1	Glass	Fragment of dark brown mouth and neck of a bottle	bottle - SAMPLE	l:4.8, 2r lip:2.9, Thick: 0.4	476-499	21/07/
65	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	C	SU 1	Glass	Fragment of a colourless window glass	window	l:2.8, thick:0.2	476-499	21/07/
66	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	C	SU 1	Metal	Iron nail	nail	l:8.0	500-514	21/07/
67	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	C	SU 1	Metal	Iron nail	nail	l:6.7	500-514	21/07/
68	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	C	SU 1	Metal	Iron nail with square body and rectangular head	nail	l:6.4	500-514	21/07/

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ID	SITE	AREA/ST	TRENCH	SU-	MATERIAL	Description/type	Object	Dimensions	Picture	date
69	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	C	SU 1	Metal	Fragment of iron chisel	chisel	l:14.0, w:1.7, thick:0.6	500-514	21/07/
70	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	C	SU 1	Organic	Sea Shell - botuto shell or Strombus giga	sea shell	l:15.5	515- 521	21/07/
71	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	C	SU 2	Cement	Cement from 108 building (STR108)	floor	Thick: 2.4cm	522-526	24/07/
72	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	C	SU2	Brick	Fragment of brick with manufacturer's mark	brick	l:9.9, height:5.7	527-532	24/07/
73	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	106	Cleanin	Metal	Iron ring	iron ring	2r:5.9, internal 2r:2.2,	533-538	24/07/
74	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	106	Cleanin	Metal	Iron closed hook	iron closed hook	l:6.1, thick:0.6	533-538	24/07/
75	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	SU1	Stoneware	Fragment of stoneware bottle	bottle	l:4.1, thick:0.7	539-553	25/07/
76	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	SU1	Porcelane	Fragment of a rim, glazed white	tableware	l:1.5, thick:0.6	539-553	25/07/
77	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	SU1	Porcelane	Fragment of a rim, glazed whiote and decortated	tableware	l:1.9,Thick: 0.5cm	539-553	25/07/
78	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	SU1	Porcelane	Fragment of white glazed tableware , with	tableware	l:1.4, thick: 0.3cm	539-553	25/07/
79	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	SU1	Glass	Fragment of colourless window glass with a corner	window	l:5.0, w:3.4, thick: 0.2	539-553	25/07/
80	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	SU1	Glass	Fragment of colourless window glass	window	l:3.6, thick:0.2	539-553	25/07/
81	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	SU1	Glass	Fragment of colourless burnt glass	unknown	l:3.4	539-553	25/07/
82	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	SU1	Glass	Fragment of colourless glassware	glassware	l:3.7, Thick: 0.3cm	539-553	25/07/
83	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	SU1	Glass	Fragment of colourless bottle base	bottle	l:4.1, thick:0.3	539-553	25/07/
84	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	SU1	Glass	Fragment of colourless glassware	glassware	l:3.5, thick:0.2	539-553	25/07/
85	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	SU1	Glass	Fragment of colourless jar with bored rim	container	l:3.1, thick:0.4	539-553	25/07/
86	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	SU1	Glass	Fragment of colourless round bottle base with	bottle	l:5.4, thick:0.8	539-553	25/07/
87	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	SU1	Glass	Fragment of colourless round bottle base with	bottle	l:4.2, thick:0.6	539-553	25/07/
88	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	SU1	Glass	Fragment of colourless bottle neck and mouth with	bottle	l:5.9, 2r lip:2.6, thick:0.5	539-553	25/07/
89	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	SU1	Glass	Fragment of green bottle mouth and neck with	bottle	l:3.5, thick:0.5	539-553	25/07/
90	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	SU1	Glass	Fragment of green bottle mouth with straight lip	bottle	l:2.9, thick:0.3-0.8	539-553	25/07/
91	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	SU1	Glass	Fragment of dark green handmade bottle with air	bottle	l:4.4, thick:0.5	539-553	25/07/
92	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	SU 1	Glass	Fragment of green base with omphalos and	bottle	l:3.8, thick:0.7	539-553	25/07/
93	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	SU1	Glass	Fragment of dark brown base of bottle with	bottle	l:5.7, thick:0.8	539-553	25/07/
94	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	SU1	Glass	Fragment of brown glassware	glassware	l:7.1, thick:0.3	539-553	25/07/
95	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	SU1	Glass	Fragment of green/blue neck of a bottle	bottle	l:6.5, thick:0.3	539-553	25/07/
96	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	SU1	Glass	Fragment of green/blue mouth with round lip	bottle	l:4.8, 2r lip:2.5, thick:0.5	539-553	25/07/
97	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	SU1	Clay	Fragment of clay bottle neck	bottle	l:2.2, thick:0.4	539-553	25/07/
98	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	SU1	Clay	Fragment of earthen lamp rim	oil lamp	l:3.9, thick:0.5	539-553	25/07/
99	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	SU1	Ardoise	Slate board with writing lines on one side	slate board	l:7.0, thick:0.2	554-560	25/07/
100	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	SU1	Glass	Fragment of green bracelet with diamond paneled	bracelet - SAMPLE	l:2.2, thick:0.3	554-560	25/07/
101	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	SU1	Bone	Fragment of the right sheep/goat humerus, with	bone	l:3.7	554-560	25/07/
102	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Glass	Glass object, with orange three-winged feather	marble - toy	2r:1.6cm	DSC_0561-63	20/07/

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ID	SITE	AREA/ST	TRENCH	SU-	MATERIAL	Description/type	Object	Dimensions	Picture	date
103	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Glass	2 Fragments of a colourless window glass	window	thickness: 0.25cm	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
104	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Glass	Fragment of a colourless window glass	window	Thick: 0.2cm	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
105	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Glass	2 Fragments of light blue glass	bottle	Thick: 0.4cm	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
106	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Glass	Fragment of dark blue glass, bottom of a small	ink bottle	2r:5cm, wall thickness:0.5	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
107	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Glass	Fragment of brown glass mouth and neck of a	bottle	2r:2.1cm, height: 3.0cm;	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
108	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Glass	Fragment of colourless glass, mouth of a bottle,	bottle	Thick: 0.3cm; 2r: 2.8cm	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
109	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Glass	Fragment of colourless glass, round base of a small	bottle	base thick:0.6cm, wall	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
110	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Glass	Fragment of colourless glass, round base of a small	bottle	base thick: 0.6cm, wall	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
111	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Glass	Fragment of colourless glass, round base and wall of	bottle	base thick: 0.4cm, wall	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
112	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Glass	Fragment of colourless glass, shaped walls of a	bottle	wall thick: 0.2cm, length:	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
113	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Glass	Fragment of colourless glass, rim of a glass with	glass/cup	wall thick: 0.25cm; 2r:	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
114	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Glass	Fragment of colourless glass, base of a glass with	glass/cup	wall thick: 0.35cm; base	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
115	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Glass	Fragment of colourless glass, wall of a bowl with	bowl	wall thick: 0.4 to 0.6cm	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
116	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Glass	Fragment of colourless glass, wall of a bowl with	bowl	wall thick: 0.7cm	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
117	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Glass	Fragment of light blue glass, rim of a bowl with	sugarbowl lid	wall thick:0.45cm, tapered	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
118	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Glass	Fragment of colourless glass, round decoration of a	bowl	wall thick:0.7cm,decor	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
119	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Glass	Fragment of green glass, round base of a small	bottle	base 2r:3.8cm, wall thick:	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
120	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Glass	Fragment of green glass, round mouth of a bottle,	bottle	lip thick:0.45,mouth 2r:2.5	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
121	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Glass	Fragment of light green glass, round base of a small	perfume bottle	wall thick:0.15, base 2r:2.0	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
122	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Glass	Fragment of green glass, round mouth and partially	bottle	wall thick:0.4; lip width:1.3	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
123	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Glass	Fragment of green glass, wall of a bottle	bottle	wall thick:0.3cm	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
124	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Glass	Fragment of dark green burned glass	unknown	thick:0.5,length:5.0, width:	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
125	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	sea shell	Kauri sea shell	sea shell	length:2.0cm	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
126	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Ceramic/cl	Fragment of earthen lamp	oil lamp	l:3.5,w:1.5,thick:0.5cm	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
127	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Ceramic/cl	Fragment of earthen lamp	oil lamp	l:2.3,w:1.8,thick:0.4cm	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
128	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Ceramic/cl	Fragment of earthen lamp	oil lamp	l:4.0,w:2.5,thick:0.5cm	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
129	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Ceramic/cl	Fragment of earthen lamp, tapered rim and part of	oil lamp	wall thick:0.7,rim thick:	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
130	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Ceramic/cl	Fragment of a large earthen lamp, tapered rim and	oil lamp	rim thick:1.4; rim length:	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
131	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Plastic	Round black button, with one hole under the top	button	2r:1.2cm	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
132	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Plastic	Sqare white button with rounded corners and two	bottle	l/w:1.9cm, thick:0.6cm	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
133	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	porcelane	3 fragments of a white/greyish glazed bowl with a	rice bowl	rim height:1.2cm,wall	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
134	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	porcelane	Fragment lf greyish glazed foot rim of a rice bowl	rice bowl	rim height: 1.6cm	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
135	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Porcelain	3 fragments of a porcelian plate with painted flower	plate	thick: 0.3,thich base:0.45,	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
136	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Porcelain	fragment fo a small bowl	bowl	wall thick:0.2,base thick:	DSC_0561-63	20/07/

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ID	SITE	AREA/ST	TRENCH	SU-	MATERIAL	Description/type	Object	Dimensions	Picture	date
137	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Porcelain	fragment fo a small bowl	bowl	foot rim thick:0.6cm	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
138	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Porcelain	frgment of a small cup, decorated with a golden	cup	base,wall thick:0.2	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
139	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Porcelain	fragment fo a foot of a tableware, decorated with	tableware	length:2.0cm	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
140	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	porcelane	fragment of a rim of a tableware, decoaretd with	tableware	length:2.0cm	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
141	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	stoneware	fragment of a stoneware plate, decortated with	tableware	l:1.7cm	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
142	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	stoneware	fragment of a stoneware plate, decortated with	tableware	l:1.4cm	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
143	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	stoneware	fragment of a stoneware rim of a plate, decorated	plate	l:l:2.2, thick:0.4cm	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
144	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Porcelain	fragment of a bottle mouth with bored lip	bottle	l:2.1cm	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
145	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Porcelain	fragment of porcelain object	unknown	l:1.8cm	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
146	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Porcelain	fragment of a shoulder of a sugar bowl, with panels	sugarbowl	l:4.1, w: 3.0 cm	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
147	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Porcelain	Fragment of a straight rim of a cup	cup	l:2.7cm	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
148	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Porcelain	Fragment of a straight rim of a cup	cup	l:3.1cm	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
149	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Porcelain	Fragment of a straight rim of a cup	cup	1.9cm	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
150	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Porcelain	6 fragemnts of porcelain cups or bowls, no	cup or bowl	/	DSC_0561-63	20/07/
151	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU2	Glass	Fragment of green glass round base with slight	bottle	base thick:0.7, height of	DSC_0013-16	23/07/
152	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU2	bone/toot	Young sheep/goat tooth	tooth	l:2.6cm	DSC_0013-16	23/07/
153	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU2	Glass	Fragment of green glass bottle mouth with	bottle	l:5.6, rim 2r:2.65; rim wall	DSC_0013-16	23/07/
154	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU2	Glass	3 Fragment of a colourless window glass	window	L:4.3, 4.8, 4.3cm	DSC_0013-16	23/07/
155	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU2	Glass	Fragment of brown glass	unknown	l:2.5cm	DSC_0013-16	23/07/
156	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU2	Ceramic/cl	4 Fragments of earthen vessel	oil lamp or	l:3.0, 3.6, 3.1,3.1cm	DSC_0013-16	23/07/
157	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU2	Ceramic/cl	2 fragments of a rim of an earthen vessel, with the	oil lamp or	l:6.3, wall thick:0.45, rim	DSC_0013-16	23/07/
158	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU2	Ceramic/cl	Fragment of a tapered rim of an earthen vessel	oil lamp or	l:5.1cm, wall thick:0.5cm	DSC_0013-16	23/07/
159	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU2	Ceramic/cl	Fragment of a rim of an earthen vessel, with the	oil lamp or	l:5.9, thcik:0.6cm	DSC_0013-16	23/07/
160	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU2	Ceramic/cl	Fragment of a rim of an earthen vessel's lid	oil lamp or	l:3.8, wall thick:0.45cm	DSC_0013-16	23/07/
161	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU2	Porcelain	6 Fragments of porcelain tableware	tableware	l:various thickness	DSC_0013-16	23/07/
162	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU2	stoneware	Fragment of stoneware tableware	tableware	l:3.3, thick:0.5cm	DSC_0013-16	23/07/
163	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU2	stoneware	Fragment of a stoneware	unknown	l: 3.2cm	DSC_0013-16	23/07/
164	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU2	stoneware	fragment of a stoneware tableware, decorated with	tableware	l:2.2cm	DSC_0013-16	23/07/
165	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU2	stoneware	Fragment of a stoneware tableware	tableware	l:1.8cm	DSC_0013-16	23/07/
166	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU2	Porcelain	3 fragments of fugurine or an ornament	ornament	l:5.2cm	DSC_0013-16	23/07/
167	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU2	Porcelain	Fragment of a handle for a small cup	handle of a cup	l:2.3cm	DSC_0013-16	23/07/
168	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU2	Porcelain	Fragment of a foot rim	tableware	l:3.1cm	DSC_0013-16	23/07/
169	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU2	Porcelain	Frgament of a rim with a small hole	unknown - a	l:3.5, 2r:about 4.2cm	DSC_0013-16	23/07/
170	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU2	Porcelain	Fragment of a rim of tableware	tableware	l:2.6cm	DSC_0013-16	23/07/

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ID	SITE	AREA/ST	TRENCH	SU-	MATERIAL	Description/type	Object	Dimensions	Picture	date
171	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU2	Porcelain	Fragment of a rim of tableware	tableware	l:2.1cm	DSC_0013-16	23/07/
172	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU2	Porcelain	2 Fragments of a rim of tableware, decorated with	tableware, maybe	l:2.0cm	DSC_0013-16	23/07/
173	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU2	Porcelain	Fragment of a rim of tableware, with black line and	tableware	l:2.4cm	DSC_0013-16	23/07/
174	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU2	Porcelain	Fragment of a rim of tableware	tableware	l:1.9cm	DSC_0013-16	23/07/
175	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU2	Glass	Fragment of colourless glass, base of a small bottle	tableware	2r:4.5; height of the foot	DSC_0013-16	23/07/
176	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU2	Glass	Fragment of colourless glass, mouth of a bottle,	bottle	l:3.7cm	DSC_0013-16	23/07/
177	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU2	Glass	Fragment of colourless glass, shaped walls of a part	lamp part ?	l:4.0cm	DSC_0013-16	23/07/
178	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU2	Glass	Fragment of colourless glass, shoulder of s bottle	bottle	l:3.8, thick:0.4cm	DSC_0013-16	23/07/
179	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU2	Glass	Fragment of colourless glass, maybe the mouth	bottle ?	l:3.0cm	DSC_0013-16	23/07/
180	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU2	Metal	Metal object with 3 hooks for holding, round in	metal box ?	l:2.0cm	DSC_0013-16	23/07/
181	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	Surfac	/	Ceramic	Decorative tile, decorated with blue and white glaze	decorative tile ?	l:4.3, w: 3.3, thick:1.1cm	DSC_0017-21	19/07/
182	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	Surfac	/	Ceramic/cl	Fragment of a large earthen lamp, tapered rim and	oil lamp or	l:6.9;rim w:2.0; rim thick:	DSC_0017-21	19/07/
183	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	Surfac	/	Ceramic/cl	Fragment of an earthen vessel	oil lamp or	l:2.5; thick:0.7cm	DSC_0017-21	19/07/
184	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	Surfac	/	Glass	Fragment of brown glass base with a 95 and a	bottle	2r:6.0, thick base:0.7, thick	DSC_0017-21	19/07/
185	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	Surfac	/	Glass	Fragment of a smaller brown glass base and wall	bottle	2r:6.0;base thick:0.5; wall	DSC_0017-21	19/07/
186	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	Surfac	/	Stoneware	Fragment of a bottom and foot rim stoneware	tableware, maybe	l:3.5; wall thick:0.7cm	DSC_0017-21	19/07/
187	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	Surfac	/	Glass	Fragment of a corner of a colourless window glass	window	l:3.2cm; thick:0.2cm	DSC_0017-21	19/07/
188	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	Surfac	/	Stoneware	Fragment of a rim of stoneware plate, decorated	plate	l:3.4; thick:0.5cm	DSC_0017-21	19/07/
189	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	Surfac	/	Stoneware	Fragment of a stoneware plate, decorated with	plate	l:1.7; thick:0.5cm	DSC_0017-21	19/07/
190	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	Surfac	/	Stoneware	Fragment of a stoneware handle of oval shape in	handle of a cup	l:2.0; thick:1.0x0.7	DSC_0017-21	19/07/
191	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	Surfac	/	Stoneware	Fragment of a stoneware bowl, decorated with	bowl	l:2.0; thick:0.3cm	DSC_0017-21	19/07/
192	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	Surfac	/	Glass	Fragment of dark blue glass, base of a small bottle	ink bottle	2r base:4.5; base thick:0.7,	DSC_0017-21	19/07/
193	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	Surfac	/	Glass	Fragment of light blue glass, with leaf relief	glassware	wall thick:0.55	DSC_0017-21	19/07/
194	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	Surfac	/	Glass	Fragment of colourless glass, neck of a bottle, with	bottle	thick:0.4, 2r neck:3.0cm	DSC_0017-21	19/07/
195	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	Surfac	/	Glass	Fragment of colourless glass, mouth of a bottle,	bottle	thick:0.4, 2r:3.1cm	DSC_0017-21	19/07/
196	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	Surfac	/	Glass	Fragment of colourless glass, base of a cup or small	cup or bottle	wall thick:0.3, base thick:	DSC_0017-21	19/07/
197	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	Surfac	/	Glass	Fragment of melted colourless glass	unknown	/	DSC_0017-21	19/07/
198	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	Surfac	/	Glass	Fragment of light green glass base, of a small	bottle	l:2.6,2r:?, base thick:0.4,	DSC_0017-21	19/07/
199	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	Surfac	/	Glass	Fragment of green mouth and round lip of a bottle,	bottle	l:3.1, lip thick:0.5	DSC_0017-21	19/07/
200	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	Surfac	/	Glass	Fragment of a green glass base of a small bottle	bottle	base thick:0.55,bulbus	DSC_0017-21	19/07/
201	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	Surfac	/	Glass	Fragment of green glass base with omphalos	bottle -wine?	wall thick:0.55	DSC_0017-21	19/07/
202	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	Surfac	/	Glass	Fragment of green base of a bottle with	bottle -wine?	base thick:0.65	DSC_0017-21	19/07/
203	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	Surfac	/	Glass	Fragment of green glass neck of a bottle	bottle	base thick:0.65	DSC_0017-21	19/07/
204	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	Surfac	/	Glass	Fragment of green base of a bottle with	bottle	base thick:0.6	DSC_0017-21	19/07/

Annex 2: Catalogue of Artefacts

ID	SITE	AREA/ST	TRENCH	SU-	MATERIAL	Description/type	Object	Dimensions	Picture	date
205	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	Surfac	/	Glass	2 Fragments of white glass mouth and straight lip of	bottle	2rbase:about3.5	DSC_0017-21	19/07/
206	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	Surfac	/	Porcelain	Fragment of bottom of a plate with low foot. In the	plate	2r base rim:6.0, base thick:	DSC_0017-21	19/07/
207	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	Surfac	/	Porcelain	Fragment of a porcelrain object	unknown	2r:about 4.7	DSC_0017-21	19/07/
208	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	Surfac	/	Porcelain	Fragment of a base of small bowl with partial wall	bowl	base thick:0.3, wall thick:	DSC_0017-21	19/07/
209	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	Surfac	/	Porcelain	Fragment of a base of small bowl with a small rim	bowl	base thick:0.2	DSC_0017-21	19/07/
210	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	Surfac	/	Porcelain	Fragment of a rim of a porcelain bowl or cup, 2mm	bowl or cup	l:1.3	DSC_0017-21	19/07/
211	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	Surfac	/	Porcelain	Fragment of a wall of porcerlain object	bowl or cup	l:1.5	DSC_0017-21	19/07/
212	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	Surfac	/	Porcelain	frgamenet of a small handle with a shoulder of a cup,	bowl or cup	l:1.5, 2r:0.5x0.6	DSC_0017-21	19/07/
213	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	Surface	Glass	3 Fragments of purple nontransparent glass	container	2r rim foot:about 4.7	DSC_0022-25	25/07/
214	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	Surface	Porcelain	Fragment of a base of a small plate, decorated with	plate	l:2.4, case thick:0.2	DSC_0022-25	25/07/
215	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	Surface	Porcelane	Fragment of a base and walls of a chinese tea cup	tea cup	2r rim foot:2.5, base thick:	DSC_0022-25	25/07/
216	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	Surface	Stoneware	Fragment of stoneware tableware with white glaze	plate	l:4.0, thick:0.5	DSC_0022-25	25/07/
217	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	Surface	Stoneware	Fragment of stoneware tableware with white glaze	plate	l:2.3, thick:0.4	DSC_0022-25	25/07/
218	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	Surface	Stoneware	Fragment of stoneware tableware with greyish	bowl	l:4.6, thick:0.6	DSC_0022-25	25/07/
219	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	Surface	Glass	Fragment of light blue glass	unknown	l:4.8, thick:0.3	DSC_0022-25	25/07/
220	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	Surface	Glass	Fragment of colourless glass, base of a cup or small	cup or bottle	l:5.4, base thick:1.1, 2r	DSC_0022-25	25/07/
221	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	Surface	Glass	Fragment of colourless glass, cbase of a bottle	bottle	2r base:6.2, base thick:1.0	DSC_0022-25	25/07/
222	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	Surface	Glass	Fragment of colourless glass, base of a cup or	cup or bottle	2r base:6.0, base thick:1.1	DSC_0022-25	25/07/
223	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	Surface	Glass	Fragment of colourless glass, base of a cup or	cup or bottle	base thick:0.6, wall thick:	DSC_0022-25	25/07/
224	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	Surface	Glass	Fragment of colourless glass, base of a cup or bottle	cup or bottle	base thick:0.55	DSC_0022-25	25/07/
225	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	Surface	Glass	Fragment of colourless glass, mouth of a bottle,	bottle	lip thick:0.5, l:2.5	DSC_0022-25	25/07/
226	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	Surface	Glass	Fragment of colourless glass, wall of a bottler or	bottle or	l:3.4; thick:0.5cm	DSC_0022-25	25/07/
227	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	Surface	Glass	Fragment of colourless glass, wall of a bottle or	bottle or	l:3.3, thuck:0.45	DSC_0022-25	25/07/
228	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	Surface	Glass	Fragment of colourless glass, wall of a bottle or	cup or bottle	l:6.3, thick:0.3-0.65	DSC_0022-25	25/07/
229	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	D	SU1	Glass	Fragment of light blue glass bracelet	bracelet - SAMPLE	l:3.5	DSC_0026-28	25/07/
230	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	Surfac	/	Bone	Round button with decorative ridge and two holes	button	2r:1.45	DSC_0030--33	25/07/
231	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Glass	7 Fragments of glass bracelets of light blue and	bracelet	l:4.5,3.9, 3.3, 3.1, 2.3, 2.4,	34-36	20/07/
232	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Plastic	Fragment of a pink bracelet with golden diamonds	bracelet	l:3.7cm	37,38	20/07/
233	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Metal	Coin for 5 cents of Mauritian rupees with Elizabeth	coin	2r:2.8	39-42	20/07/
234	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Glass	Fragment of light green bowl decotared with relief	bowl	l:3.6, wall thick:0.4	43-48	20/07/
235	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU2	Glass	Fragments of light blue bracelets	bracelet	l:3.2, 2.2	52	21/07/
236	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU2	Glass	Green bead	bead - SAMPLE	2r:0.3	53,54	21/07/
237	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU2	Glass	Fragment of a brown bracelet	bracelet - SAMPLE	l:3.3	55-57	21/07/
238	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU2	Metal	Bronze or silver coin, bent because it was pushed	coin - SAMPLE	2r:2.0	49-51	21/07/

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ID	SITE	AREA/ST	TRENCH	SU-	MATERIAL	Description/type	Object	Dimensions	Picture	date
239	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	C	SU1	Glass	Fragment of a colourless window glass	window	l:3.4; thick:0.5cm	58-60	21/07/
240	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	C	SU1	Glass	Fragment of dark grey glass	unknown	l:2.3, thick:0.1	58-60	21/07/
241	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	C	SU1	Metal	Iron screw with a a bronze washer	screw	2r:1.7	58,59,62,63	21/07/
242	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	C	SU1	Plastic	Red oval gem	decoration	oval:0.7 x 0.95, thick:0.3	58,59	21/07/
243	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	C	SU1	Glass	Fragments of glass bracelets of light blue and yellow	bracelet	l:2.1, 1.5, 1.3,	58,59,61	21/07/
244	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	C	SU1	Glass	Glass bottle stopper in the shape of heksagon with	stopper - SAMPLE	l:4.1, w:2.3, thick:1.0, 2r of	66,67,68	21/07/
245	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	C	SU1	Glass	Fragment of a small cupwith 5-arm star shaped	cup - SAMPLE	l:4.0, 2r base:3.1, wall	66,67,69-71	21/07/
246	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	C	SU1	Bone	Mandibule of a goat with teeth	mandibule - goat	l:7.5	72-74	21/07/
247	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Metal	Iron rods	metal rods		337-341	23/07/
248	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Metal	Iron nails	nails		342,343	23/07/
249	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Metal	Iron rods	iron rods		344,345	23/07/
250	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU1	Metal	iron bosses	iron bosses		346	23/07/
251	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU2	Metal	Iron nails	nails		347	23/07/
252	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU2	Metal	Iron rods	bosses		348,349	23/07/
253	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU2	Metal	iron bosses	iron rods		350-353	20/07/
254	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU2	Metal	metal paddle lock	paddle lock		354-357	20/07/
255	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	A	SU2	Metal	Metal buckle - maybe for a bag?	buckle		358	20/07/
256	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU1	Metal	Iron nails	nails		359-361	21/07/
257	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU1	Metal	Metal rods and cilinder objects	unknown		362,363	21/07/
258	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU1	Metal	Iron rods	iron rods		364	21/07/
259	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU1	Metal	metal lock ?			365	24/07/
260	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU1	Metal	metal round object			366	24/07/
261	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU1	Metal	Frgaments of metal of objects	unknown		367-369	20/07/
262	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU2	Metal	iron rods	rods		370	21/07/
263	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	B	SU2	Metal	Iron nails	nails		371, 372	20/07/
264	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	C	SU1	Metal	Iron bosses	bosses		373	25/07/
265	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	C	SU1	Metal	Metal cilinder	cilinder?		374	25/07/
266	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	C	SU1	Metal	Iron nails	nails		375	25/07/
267	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	C	SU2	Metal	iron bosses			376,377	25/07/
268	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	C	SU2	Metal	Metal forks	forks		378	25/07/
269	Phooliyar	CAMP 1	C	SU2	Metal	Iron rods	rods		379	25/07/